

Work package 4: Socio-ecological management framework for MPAs and MSP integration

D4.1: Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs

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Abstract	This report presents preliminary results from a methodology aimed at defining socio-economic and governance criteria for prioritizing proposals related to new areas, boundary adjustments, area relocations, and network corridors within marine management approaches. The study also focuses on identifying Ecosystem Services (ES) that encompass the social dimensions of various	

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Keywords

spatial management approaches in the marine realm. This method allows quantifying nature's significance to human communities, bridging the gap between human activities and the services provided by ecosystems. The objectives of this study are centred on defining essential socio-economic and governance criteria, identifying the corresponding ecosystem services, and assessing their societal values within the socio-ecological system of a specific area, thus enhancing the effectiveness of different marine management processes (e.g., Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) and Marine Protected Area (MPA)).

Socio-economic and governance criteria; Ecosystem Services Valuation; Marine Spatial Planning; Marine Protected Area

History of Changes

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1.0	31 October 2023	Initial version
2.0	31 August 2024	Modified following reviewer comments. The definition of "blue economy activities" has been clarified, specifying which activities are included and how this criterion is distinguished from other specific sector criteria. A brief explanation under Step 7 now clarifies that each criterion was analyzed separately, addressing their independence during data analysis. Additionally, the revised text explains how other human activities not explicitly covered under the socioeconomic criteria list are integrated into the framework, ensuring it remains adaptable and applicable to different contexts. An acknowledgment section has also been included in this version, and test site leads have been added as authors.

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Acronyms

ACCOBAMS_CCH	Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans of the Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and contiguous Atlantic area - Cetaceans Critical Habitats
AZOR	Azores
BlackSeaC	Black Sea Commission
CBD	Convention on Biological Diversity
CFP	Common Fisheries Policy
CICES	Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services
CoP	Community of Practice
DEVOTES indicators	DEvelopment Of innovative Tools for understanding marine biodiversity and assessing good Environmental Status
EB-MSP	Ecosystem-based Marine Spatial Planning
EBM	Ecosystem-based Management
EBSAs	Ecologically or Biologically Important Marine Areas
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variables
EC-CINEA	European Commission - Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
EEA	European Environment Agency
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
ES	Ecosystem Services
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
GBRMP	Great Barrier Reef Marine Park
GEF	Global Environmental Facility
GEO BON	Group on Earth Observations - Biodiversity Observation Networks
HELCOM	Helsinki Commission for the Marine Environmental Protection of the Baltic Sea
HP	High priority
IBA	Important Bird Areas
IGO	Intergovernmental Organization
IMMAs	Important Marine Mammal Areas
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IMO - PSSAs	International Maritime Organization - Particularly Sensitive Sea Areas
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission

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LP	Low priority
MJ	Majority Judgement
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MS	Microsoft
MSFD	Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP	Maritime Spatial Planning
MSPD	Marine Spatial Planning Directive
N	Neutral
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NP	Not a priority
NW-Med	North-West - Mediterranean
OECMs	Other Effective Conservation Measures
OSPAR	Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic
P	Priority
REPCET tool	Real time plotting of cetaceans
RESPA	Rapid Ecosystem Services Participatory Appraisal
SCI	Site of Community Importance
SER	Society for Ecological Restoration
SPA/RAC	Regional Activity Centre for Specially Protected Areas
SPAMI list	List of Specially Protected Areas of Mediterranean Importance
UCA	University of Cadiz
UICN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
UK	United Kingdom
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization
WCPA	World Commission on Protected Areas
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WWF	World Wildlife Fund
ZEC	Special Areas of Conservation (acronym in Spanish)

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Glossary

Criteria. A standard or principle for judging, evaluating, or selecting something: in this case, Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) and Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP). Particular requirements must be met in order to be considered or qualify. As mentioned by the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) (2017), may be set down, providing guidance for future development, such as environmental considerations that should be taken into account. This use of criteria for MSP, can be easily extended to MPA and the social, economic and governance pillar, which is the approach used and recommended for this guideline.

Conservation. The protection, management, and maintenance of ecosystem, species, and populations to safeguard the conditions that ensure their long-term survival IUCN. (2021)

Ecosystem Services. Ecosystem services are defined as the contributions that ecosystems make to human well-being, and distinct from the goods and benefits that people subsequently derive from them. These contributions are framed in terms of 'what ecosystems do' for people (Haines-Young and Potschin, 2018).

Other effective area-based Conservation Measures (OECM). This means "a geographically defined area other than a Protected Area, which is governed and managed in ways that achieve positive and sustained long-term outcomes for the in-situ conservation of biodiversity, with associated ecosystem functions and services and where applicable, cultural, spiritual, socio-economic, and other locally relevant values" (CBD/COP/DEC/14/8 30 November 2018).

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Executive Summary

This report presents preliminary results from a methodology aimed at defining socio-economic and governance criteria for prioritizing proposals related to new areas, boundary adjustments, area relocations, and network corridors within marine management approaches. The study also focuses on identifying Ecosystem Services (ES) that encompass the social dimensions of various spatial management approaches in the marine realm. This method allows quantifying nature's significance to human communities, bridging the gap between human activities and the services provided by ecosystems. The objectives of this study are centred on defining essential socio-economic and governance criteria, identifying the corresponding ecosystem services, and assessing their societal values within the socio-ecological system of a specific area, thus enhancing the effectiveness of different marine management processes (e.g., Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) and Marine Protected Area (MPA)). The preliminary outcomes of this research will be integrated into the ESE Framework of the MSP4Bio project. More specifically, it supports the other tasks of the MSP4Bio project as Task 4.2. “Strategic and Spatial measures for blue economy sectors”; Task 4.3. “Participatory development of the integrated trade-offs scenarios”; Task 4.4. “MPAs and MSP Ecological-Socio-Economic integrated management framework”; and Task 6.1. “Analysis of the EU, regional seas and national approaches to implement the marine biodiversity policies”.

1. Introduction

1.1. MPAs and MSP

The effects of human coastal and maritime activities often combine into cumulative impacts on many marine ecosystems (Halpern et al., 2015, Halpern et al., 2008). As Zupan et al. (2018) pointed out, Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) represent the most common approach used to mitigate human impacts on marine ecosystems (Lubchenco and Grorud-Colvert, 2015; Lubchenco et al., 2003) and are being increasingly used worldwide both for conservation and fisheries management (Boonzaier and Pauly, 2015).

MPAs are, as the name implies, designated areas in the ocean within which human activities are regulated more stringently than elsewhere in the marine environment (Ussif et al., 2019). They are defined by the World Conservation Union (IUCN) as parts of intertidal or subtidal environments, together with their overlying waters, flora and fauna and other features, that have been reserved and protected by law or other effective means (IUCN-WCPA, 2008). Such areas are carved out to maintain, at least to some extent, the natural environment of the designated area for ecological, economic, cultural, social, recreational, and other reasons. The protection afforded by MPAs can vary widely, from minimal protection to full protection, that is, no-take reserves. In Driedger et al. (2023) it is developed that MPA have been found to provide significant conservation benefits, from which socio-economic benefits are derived (Zupan et al., 2018).

It is important to mention that establishing MPA often leads to conflicts due to divergent interests, values, perceptions, and objectives among individuals, groups, or institutions (Cárnovas-Molina and Garcia-Frapolli, 2020). Cárnovas-Molina and Garcia-Frapolli (2020) identified five primary categories into which these conflicts can be classified: i) constrained socio-economic development; ii) limited communication and participation; iii) non-compliance; iv) imposition of exogenous objectives; and v) access restrictions. However, a global study conducted by Ben et al. (2019) revealed a more positive outlook on the well-being outcomes of MPAs. The study indicated that 51% of cases exhibited positive outcomes, while 31% experienced negative consequences. Moreover, the research highlighted significant variations in outcomes based on the specific type of MPA implemented. In this sense, for the purpose of a MPA to be effective, those regulatory efforts must be accompanied by complex enabling conditions, such as enforcement, monitoring of results, long-term political commitment, sustainable financing, community participation, and benefits sharing (Grorud-Colvert et al., 2021). In practice, however, MPAs are only widely mentioned in statutes or regional/national legislation (Sletten et al., 2021), but in many cases they are not adequately accompanied by sufficiently active or effective management (Grau-Tomás and García-Sanabria, 2023).

MPAs are Ecosystem-Based Management (EBM) tools that have evolved on a global scale, both in technical sophistication and geographical coverage, thanks especially to the impetus of the Convention on Biological Diversity, an international, legally binding treaty. In its edition in Rio de Janeiro (Brazil), in 1992, basic conceptual aspects were consolidated. At the Aichi meeting (Japan), in 2010, progress was made with 20 key goals. Goal 11 stands out, which urged signatory countries to protect 10%

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of marine and coastal areas by 2020, “through of effectively and equitably managed, ecologically representative and well-connected protected area systems”. Despite its limited success, it has facilitated a key advance on a global scale and recently, in its December 2022 edition, in Canada, these objectives were reviewed, creating the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, with which, among other things, it is intended to expand this scope of protection to 30% (Driedger et al., 2023; CBD, 2021).

On this global scale, the need to extend this type of protection beyond border waters is already being addressed. Last March, a “Draft agreement within the framework of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the conservation and sustainable use of marine biological diversity in areas beyond national jurisdiction” was finalized, in which framework of “The Intergovernmental Conference on an International Legally Binding Instrument within the Framework of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea on the Conservation and Sustainable Use of Marine Biological Diversity in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction (Resolution 72/249 of the General Assembly, December 24, 2017), known as the High Seas Treaty (Guerreiro et al., 2023).

In parallel, other international and regional agreements have promoted these efforts in more specific areas. The Barcelona Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Zone of the Mediterranean, the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Northeast Atlantic (OSPAR) or the Helsinki Commission for the Marine Environmental Protection of the Baltic Sea (HELCOM) and the Convention on the Protection of the Black Sea Against Pollution (Black Sea Commission), among others, are especially notable. The European Union (EU) has included all those efforts in its regional regulations, among which the Habitats Directive (Directive 92/43/EEC), the Birds Directive (Directive 2009/147/EC) and, more specifically for the marine environment, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) (Directive 2008/56/EC) and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (Directive 2014/89/EU). On the top of it, and framing the purpose of MSP4Bio Project, comes the European Green Deal and the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework.

In conclusion, MPAs are essential tools to protect and conserve our local and global marine and ocean ecosystems. Additionally, over the last decades they have been complemented with a range of complementary tools. In this sense, relatively few decades ago, the idea of MSP emerged conceptually.

MSP is defined as “a public process of analysing and allocating the spatial and temporal distribution of human activities in marine areas to achieve ecological, economic, and social objectives that usually have been specified through a political process” (Ehler and Douvère, 2009). MSP provides an integrated planning framework that moves away from sectoral management to address multiple objectives related to achieving economic and ecological sustainability and the need to reduce conflicts in marine environment (Agardi et al., 2011). MSP has been also defined as a “process of analysing and allocating parts of the three-dimensional marine spaces to specific uses, to achieve ecological, economic and social objectives that are usually specified

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through the political process; the MSP process usually results in a comprehensive plan or vision for a marine region” (Ehler and Douvère, 2007).

MSP has spread worldwide in the last years, and the EU has been at the forefront of MSP implementation. As Guerreiro (2021) states, this is due to the needs established in the Integrated Maritime Policy [Blue Book (COM (2007) 0575)] (EC, 2007) followed by the Marine and Maritime Agenda for Growth (EC, 2012), which introduced the Blue Growth Strategy. In this framework, the EU's Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD) was adopted in 2014, requiring EU member states to develop maritime spatial plans by 2021. The directive aims to promote sustainable development and environmental protection in Europe's marine waters by providing a framework for cooperation between member states. The directive also aims to ensure that MSP is integrated into other EU policies, such as the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) and the MSFD.

The relationship between MSP and MPAs is strong but not always explicitly recognized (Trouillet and Jay, 2021). MPAs are one of the tools that can be used to achieve conservation objectives within MSP. The allocation of space within MSP can be used to identify areas that are suitable for protection as MPAs. In this way, MSP can help ensure that MPAs are designated in areas where they will be most effective in achieving conservation objectives. MSP's area designations such as high nature value areas can enhance nature conservation also outside of formal MPAs (Vaughan and Agardy, 2020).

In this sense, as is pointed in Frazao Santos et al. (2019), the concept of MSP emerged almost 40 years ago in the context of marine conservation planning, having its roots in the zoning plan of the Great Barrier Reef Marine Park (GBRMP) in Australia. However, as they pointed, as MSP spread worldwide, its conservation foundation has in some instances become diluted shifting toward an increasing need to manage conflicting maritime uses, both existing and future, especially in crowded ocean spaces and highly industrial maritime areas (Young et al., 2007).

Despite this evolution observed in MSP operationalisation, at a theoretical level it has been increasingly recognized as one of the processes for effective implementation of an EBM of maritime use (Ansong et al., 2017). MSP is supposed to ensure that maritime uses are planned to be compatible, considering ecosystem services by harmonizing ecological, economic and social objectives. In this way, ecosystem-based MSP (EB-MSP) aims to the maintenance of marine ecosystems in a healthy condition, the sustainable exploitation of ecosystem goods and services, the reduction of conflicts among competing uses of the maritime territory, and the provision of multiple benefits to an as wide as possible array of involved sectors (Katsanevakis et al., 2011).

1.2. Socio-ecosystem approach in MPA/MSP

Since 1990, particularly since the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment in 2005, the concept of Ecosystem Services (ES) has gained global interest. In recent years, has been triggered the need to conceive ecosystems as socio-ecosystems, due to the constant interaction and connection between natural and anthropized ecosystems. Progress is towards the implementation of EBM measures that enable the recovery and conservation of biodiversity and the integrity of the oceans (García-Sanabria, 2014; Olsen et al., 2014; García-Sanabria et al., 2021).

Developing a social preference framework for ES based on individual preferences holds particular significance for public policies aimed at environmental management and spatial planning (Sy et al., 2022). This approach serves as a mean to enhance the decision-making processes of our societies and public bodies, allowing us to better shape the relationship with nature (Salles and Figuières, 2012).

As stated by Brussard et al. (1998), ecosystem management entails the strategic management of areas at various scales, aiming to conserve ecological services and biological resources while sustaining appropriate human uses. The identification of these preferences plays a pivotal role in tailoring policy measures and incentives to be more specific, thus increasing their acceptance among the population. By determining which services are deemed important by stakeholders, a more precise understanding of their perceptions can be achieved and, consequently, the value they place on these ecosystem services.

Environmental economics and ecological economics have raised the question of how to assess the value of natural assets, the amenities they generate, and the goods and services derived from ecosystems. The environmental economics approach, which relies greatly on Cost-Benefit analysis—a monetary approach—seems to have limited applicability in actual decision-making (Rey-Valette et al., 2017). The approach of ecological economics not only recognizes the economic importance of nature but also considers its social and cultural significance, along with the ethical principles governing the relationship between nature and society beyond mere utility. The first two approaches primarily frame environmental policy in terms of economic incentives.

One of the key principles behind MSP is the recognition of ecosystem services, theoretically. Ecosystem services are the benefits that humans derive from the natural environment, and they are crucial for our well-being and economic prosperity. In the context of MSP, understanding and valuing these services is paramount (Douvere, 2008).

By integrating these ecosystem services into MSP, policymakers, stakeholders, and communities can make informed decisions promoting sustainability, economic growth, and the preservation of valuable marine environments (Atkins, et al., 2011). Being a holistic approach, MSP recognizes both the interconnectedness of activities and the need to protect the services our oceans provide for current and future generations.

One of the primary purposes of MPAs is to ensure the preservation of ES in marine environments. Some examples highlight the importance of the ecosystem approach in MPAs, mainly regarding biodiversity conservation, because MPAs act as refuges for marine species, allowing them to thrive without the constant pressures of fishing,

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habitat destruction, and pollution. This preservation of biodiversity is crucial for the stability and resilience of marine ecosystems.

Moreover, MPAs designation could support fisheries enhancement, by protecting breeding grounds and fish habitats within MPAs, these areas can serve as a natural source for replenishing fish stocks outside their boundaries. This "spillover effect" benefits fisheries and ensures a sustainable supply of seafood.

Another ecosystem service highlighted in MPAs is climate change mitigation. Healthy marine ecosystems in MPAs can sequester carbon dioxide and help mitigate the impacts of climate change (Hoegh-Guldberg et al., 2019). Coral reefs, seagrass beds, and mangroves, often found in MPAs, are especially effective at capturing and storing carbon.

A MPA has different types of protection that can vary from fully protected to Minimally protected according to the uses and activities and their intensity allowed within MPA (Grorud-Colvert et al. 2021). A common categorization of MPA, and the one used in this work, is the one provided by International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) (Table I). In this sense, although MPAs are conservation areas, activities associated with leisure and tourism can take place in them, depending on the type of MPA. Many MPAs are popular destinations for recreational activities such as snorkelling, diving, and wildlife watching. These activities contribute to local economies, providing jobs and income while promoting environmental awareness and conservation. Other cultural services are important in MPAs, such as research and education, as MPAs serve as living laboratories for scientists to study marine life and ecosystems. This research enhances our understanding of the oceans and helps inform conservation strategies worldwide. Additionally, MPAs provide opportunities for education and outreach, raising public awareness about the value of marine ecosystems.

Table 1: IUCN's Protected Areas Management Categories, which classify protected areas according to their management objective. Source: Dudley (2008).

IUCN MPA	Name	Description
i-a	Strict nature reserve	Strict protection
i-b	Wilderness area	Strict protection
ii	National park	Ecosystem conservation and protection
iii	National monument or feature	Conservation of natural monument or feature
iv	Habitat/species management area	Conservation through active management
v	Protected landscapes or seascapes	Landscape/seascape conservation and recreation
vi	Protected areas with sustainable use of natural resources	Sustainable use of natural resources

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The establishment and effective management of MPAs are essential for balancing human activities with the preservation of ecosystem services. By designating and protecting these areas, we can ensure the long-term health of our oceans, support sustainable fisheries, mitigate climate change impacts, and provide numerous benefits to both nature and society (EEA, 2015). As the global community recognizes the value of these protected zones, efforts to expand and strengthen MPAs continue to play a crucial role in marine conservation and the sustainable use of ocean and seas.

1.3. The social dimension

A number of studies developed on ecosystem services have allowed to expand theoretical knowledge on the subject (Müller et al., 2010), and to develop detailed classifications based on systems theory (Potschin & Haines-Young, 2016; Santos-Martin et al., 2018). Such research is of great importance for understanding the relationships between ecosystems and the services they potentially provide. However, in many cases, the complexity of the models leads to a lack of applicability in space, and even more so for decision-making by coastal and marine managers (Müller et al., 2020).

For both MSP and MPA designation, characterising the services provided by different ecosystems provides guidance for future MPA planning and zoning scenarios. In this way, the services that are identified for each of the ecosystems should not only be done theoretically and from literature references, but a participatory process is necessary to reinforce the results obtained (Maund et al., 2020).

In this context, the social dimension explores questions of access to marine resources, equitable distribution of benefits, cultural heritage preservation, and the impacts of MSP on local economies and ways of life. As we delve into the intricacies of maritime spatial planning, it becomes clear that the successful management of the ocean and coastal areas hinges not only on ecological considerations, rather than on achieving a harmonious balance between human activities and the preservation of marine ecosystems. This introduction sets the stage for a deeper exploration of the multifaceted aspects of the social dimension within the framework of MSP.

In this sense, to facilitate effective decision-making, it is essential to foster values that motivate individuals to actively engage in pro-environmental actions, both on an individual and collective level. Incorporating stakeholder perceptions of ecosystem services emerges as a critical step in assessing their recognition within society and understanding their relative importance within a specific geographical context (Rey-Valette et al., 2017). This approach not only enhances the decision-making process but also equips decision-makers with valuable insights to anticipate potential conflicts (see Cárnovas-Molina and Garcia-Frapolli (2020)) and provides them with robust data and arguments for informed trade-off assessments. The knowledge and awareness of services through perception surveys are strategic for the implementation of environmental policies, but research on this matter is little developed.

The existence of an ecosystem service depends on the existence of an actual (direct and indirect) use, a potential demand, or the recognition of value (non-use value). All the methods for ecosystem service valuation must deal with the fact that their

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contribution to social welfare is determined by demand or actual use, even if beneficiaries are not always aware of it.

The Statement-based valuation quantifies or qualifies the importance of nature for people based on what people state about the importance of nature and human-nature relationship. The valuation is mainly based on interviews, surveys, or group discussions (Termansen et al., 2022).

The focus will be on instrumental and relational values. The former is associated with living and non-living entities, as means to achieve human ends or satisfy human preferences. As means to an end, instrumental values are in principle replaceable, albeit not always in practice. The latter is the value of desirable, meaningful, and often reciprocal human relationships with nature, which are often specified as a particular landscape, place, species, forest, etc., and among people through nature (Anderson et al, 2022).

1.4. Objectives

“T4.1 will define the socio-economic criteria that allow prioritising the proposal of new areas, new limits; reallocation of areas; network corridors, etc. It will identify Ecosystem Services (ES) that can cover the social dimension of the identification and management of MPAs, including as part of the MSP processes, revenue, and non-revenue generating ES, pinpointing those that bring the most societal value, in terms of the establishment of MPAs, without discarding the less representative ones (in terms of social impact). At the end of the task, criteria will be delivered to choose those ES representing social dimensions to be applied for better-protected area management and MSP process.”

General Objective

The following methodological framework was developed with the aim to identify socio-economic criteria in the process of MPAs establishment and management and the MSP process; identification of the ecosystem services and the societal value associated with MPA, building upon the work of Withouck *et al.* (2023) - *Summary report of existing criteria, species and habitat lists used in conservation and restoration initiatives. version 31/07/2023. Deliverable 2.2, MSP4BIO project.*

Specific objectives

- Identification of socio-economic criteria utilised (or with potential) on the creation, extension, and management of MPA;
- Identification of potential socio-economic and governance criteria common to MPA and MSP processes;
- Identification of ES with most societal value and associated criteria;
- Based on test sites results achieved, develop conclusions and recommendations.

2. Methodology

The methodology proposed is based on the perceptions of diverse stakeholders which allows establishing a ranking of relevant and interlinked ecosystem services, socio-economic and governance criteria. It aims to respond to the need for operational tools that integrate the perceptions of actors and inhabitants to help spatial planning decisions. The methodology is also built upon the different European Union policies and international agreements.

Figure 1 summarises the methodology followed to identify and rank the most important governance, socio-economic criteria and its related ecosystem services in each of the six test sites included in MSP4BIO project.

Figure 1: Methodological summary.

2.1. Development of a methodology for the incorporation of socio-economic criteria in the creation/development/expanding MPAs.

Identifying socio-economic criteria for incorporation into the process of MPAs creation/development, while aligning them with the MSP approach, aids in harmonising these processes within the diverse European marine regions, each often subject to varying policies and institutions.

This effort seeks to leverage existing socio-economic criteria found in different directives, instructions, and international documents (see Annex I). To this end, the work started from the criteria list provided by the project (Withouck *et al.* 2023, *Summary report of existing criteria, species and habitat lists used in conservation and restoration initiatives. version 31/07/2023. Deliverable 2.2, MSP4BIO project*).

STEP 1 - CATEGORIZING AND ANALYSING CRITERIA AND ASSOCIATED ECOSYSTEM SERVICES

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It is based on the list of socio-economic, environmental and governance criteria identified by Task 2.2 and Task 4.3 of the MSP4BIO project. The original list included around one thousand criteria coming from relevant policies, directives, legislations, and international documents (Withouck et al. 2023). At this step, two tasks were performed:

Task 1. Selecting and analysing socio-economic criteria

To perform this task, it was first necessary to identify and select the criteria related to socio-economic and governance issues from the provided list of criteria. Secondly, we proceeded by analyzing each selected criterion to better aggregate them into a final list of 20 socio-economic and 12 governance criteria for creating and/or developing a Marine Protected Area (see Annex II). This final list of 32 criteria retains the technical nature of the text from the original documents while making it more concise and user-friendly for stakeholder engagement. Tables 2 and 3 present the definitive results of this process, offering a comprehensive overview of each socio-economic and governance criterion on which the next steps of this methodology are based. These tables also link each criterion to its respective source, whether it be a report and/or legislation from which it originated. It is important to highlight that the definition of the term "blue economy" used in this work is the one established by the European Commission (2018), which states that "Blue economy refers to all economic activities related to oceans, seas, and coasts. It encompasses a wide range of interlinked established and emerging sectors." The blue economy sectors selected for exploring ecosystem services in this analysis were chosen based on their economic or cultural significance for the test sites, as identified through stakeholder feedback and existing data sources, including the work of Withouck et al. (2023). This process is detailed in the next steps (STEP 3).

Table 2: Socio-economic criteria selection and source of information.

Socio-economic criteria	Legislation and Report related
Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities	WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b)
Area is important for fishery activity	WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); MSFD Annex III Table 1; IMO PSSAs; DEVOTES indicators
Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	WWF (2021); WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); Ehler (2014); EC-CINEA et al. (2022); Criteria descriptors MSFD
Area is important for shipping	MSFD Annex III Table 1; HD Annex III: CRITERIA FOR SELECTING SITES ELIGIBLE FOR IDENTIFICATION AS SITES OF COMMUNITY IMPORTANCE AND DESIGNATION AS SPECIAL AREAS OF CONSERVATION; IMO PSSAs; ACCOBAMS_CCH; DEVOTES indicators
Area is important for dredging.	Ehler (2014); SPAMI List; DEVOTES indicators

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Area is important for locally caught seafood	Ehler (2014); IMO PSSAs
Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.	Ehler (2014); WWF (2021); IMO PSSAs; UNESCO; SPAMI List
The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.	IMO PSSAs
Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.	UNESCO; IMO PSSAs; SPAMI List
Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.	WWF (2021); Ehler (2014); IMO PSSAs
Area important for recreation and leisure.	Ehler (2014); IMO PSSAs; SPAMI List; MSFD Annex III Table 1
Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.	WWF (2021); Ehler (2014); UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021); IMO PSSAs; UNCLOS identification of areas for protection; SPAMI List
Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural. (monuments, etc)	IMO PSSAs; UNESCO; WWF (2021)
Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	Ehler (2014)
Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.	WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); IMO PSSAs; ACCOBAMS_CCH; SPAMI List; MSFD Annex III Table 1
Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.	Authors expert criteria
Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.	WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); WWF (2021)
Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes	IMO PSSAs; SPAMI List; MSFD Annex III Table 1
Area is important for educational interest	IMO PSSAs; SPAMI List
An area that has high scientific interest.	WWF (2021); Ehler (2014); IMO PSSAs; SPAMI List

Table 3: Governance criteria selection and source of information.

GOVERNANCE CRITERIA	Legislation and Report related
Ecosystem-based management approach	WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); Ehler (2014); UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021); Ocean's criteria set for selection of essential fish habitats; SPAMI List; MSFD Annex III Table 1
Long term strategic adaptive management	WWF (2021); UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021); WWF (2021); WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); Bird Life International (2022)

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Coherent management of the area	WWF (2021); WWF European Policy Office, 2022b; UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021); SPAMI List
Stakeholder participation	WWF (2021); Ehler (2014); UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021); SPAMI List; Criteria WNBR Statutory Framework Art.9
Equity	WWF (2021); Ehler (2014); UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021)
Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies	Criteria WNBR Statutory Framework Art.10; WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); Ehler (2014); WWF (2021)
Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy	WWF (2021); Ehler (2014); EC-CINEA et al. (2022)
Sustainable fishing management	
Climate change measures established	WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); EC-CINEA et al. (2022); Appendix III - Criteria and procedures for designation of SOx emission control areas (Regulation 14)
Cross-border cooperation	WWF (2021); WWF (2022); WWF European Policy Office (2022a); WWF European Policy Office (2022b); EC-CINEA et al. (2022); Black Sea species list criteria
Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available	WWF (2021), UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021)
Strategic Environmental Assessment	WWF (2021), UNESCO-IOC/European Commission (2021)
Monitoring and evaluation	WWF (2021); Ehler (2014)

Task 2. Linking socio-economic criteria with Ecosystem Services

To facilitate the perception analysis of the relation of every socio-economic criterion with the Ecosystem Services (to be done in step 2), a group of four experts on socio-ecologic systems from the University of Cádiz performed an initial analysis of potential relations between the criteria and the Ecosystem Services (Table 4).

Table 4: Example of criteria and its related Ecosystem services.

Criterion	Area is important for fishery activity (e.g., priority stocks)	
	The area is important for fishing, which occurs in that place or has the potential for it to occur. The area could also be important to the sector because it presents characteristics and conditions that sustain the fishery in another area, e. g., because it is a breeding and spawning zone.	
Associated Ecosystem Services	Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi;	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,

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Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	The genetic information that is stored in wild animals that we can use
	Plants, fungi or algae that we can use for breeding
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Polinization (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersion.
Pest and disease control	Controlling pests, invasive species and diseases

STEP 2 - SELECTING IMPORTANT CRITERIA THROUGH PERCEPTION ANALYSIS

First, a selection of a current MPA inside of each test site should be made by every test site leader. The selected MPA should be familiar to most of the CoP members of the case study.

To perform this task, the principle of Criteria Majority Judgment (MJ) was used. The respondents explicitly express their opinions on the merit of every Criterion on a common ordinal scale of measurement, which were in our case defined as: “high priority”, “priority”, “neutral”, “low priority” and “not a priority” (Table 5).

This exercise was designed to collect the opinion of the CoP members in every test site. Their opinion should be based on the following conditions:

- The criterion helps to define and/or modify coastal and marine areas for conservation purposes (natural or cultural heritage);
- It helps to order uses and activities in a marine area (both for MSP and for MPA zoning);
- It helps the management process for conservation and/or for the planning of uses and activities.

Once the respondents have established the priority of each criterion for their case study, they are asked to rank those selected as high priority (HP) and priority (P). It is noteworthy that the criterion "Area is important for the development of blue economy activities" was used to cover other sectors not included as separate criteria. In other words, this criterion was applied more broadly to represent sectors not specifically listed as individual criteria. For example, even though "renewable energy" is not an

explicit criterion, its relevance can be captured under this general criterion, thus addressing the particularities of different areas and regions.

Table 5: Prioritisation example of criteria as “high priority”, “priority”, “neutral”, “low priority” and “not a priority”, and ranking those criteria selected as High priority and priority (See Annex III to access to the complete Table).

Priority	Ranking	Socio-economic criteria	Examples (from previous criteria)
		Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to non-traditional activities	The area is (or can be) an important source of income and industrial jobs at industrial scale.
		Area is important for fishery activity	The area is important for fishing, which occurs in that place or has the potential for it to occur. The area could also be important to the sector because it presents characteristics and conditions that sustain the fishery in another area, e.g., because it is a breeding and spawning zone.
		Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	The area has relevant characteristics that facilitate or support specific activities related to the blue economy (aquaculture, offshore wind farm, biotechnology, tourism, ...)

STEP 3 - LINKING SOCIO-ECONOMIC CRITERIA AND ECOSYSTEM SERVICES THROUGH PERCEPTION ANALYSIS

While policy documents are increasingly considering human well-being, which encompasses social, economic, governance, and health dimensions (Ban et al., 2019), the integration of well-being with nature remains relatively underdeveloped (Science for Environment and Policy, 2018). Ecosystem services emerge as a vital means to bridge this gap, as they are fundamentally essential to the well-being of all individuals in every location (McMichael et al., 2005). As highlighted in the introduction, recognizing their linkages with the socio-economic criteria employed in the designation and evaluation of MPAs and MSP can greatly enhance the decision-making process during negotiations, trade-offs, and stakeholder engagement efforts.

Therefore, this step is focused on making the existing relations between the socio-economic criteria with the ES in each of the six case studies of the MSP4BIO project. To do so, we have used the Ecosystem Services provided by the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services from the column GROUP (Annex IV).

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With some adaptations to adjust the needs of the MSP4Bio project, the perception analysis is based on the method “The Rapid Ecosystem Services Participatory Appraisal (RESPA)” developed by Rey-Valette et al. (2017) which is a method of valuing ecosystem services based on perception surveys. The work of Sy et al. (2022) on the valuation of ecosystem services and social choice is also considered.

Every criterion identified as High Priority and Priority in step 2 is now related with the associated ecosystem services. The CoP members should rank those ES in order of its importance in their MPAs (Table 6). It is possible to add other ES if the CoP members think some are missing, but those ES should be based the ones listed in the Table provided in Annex IV.

Table 6: Example of the ranking exercise. All the Tables utilised can be consulted in Annex V.

Criterion	Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities		Ranking
	The area is (or can be) an important source of income and industrial jobs at industrial scale.< activities		
Associated Ecosystem services	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source	
	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food , materials or energy from wild plants.	
	Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,	
		The genetic information that is stored in wild animals that we can use	
		Plants. fungi or algae that we can use for breeding	
	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	
	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	
	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g., salt)	
	Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	The ways the physical environment contribute to human (e.g., wind energy, ozone, sunlight)	
	Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	

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Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Water used as: drinking water, material and no-drinking (e.g., cooling) and energy (e.g., tidal)	
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Polinizacion (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersa.	
Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	

STEP 4 - SELECTING IMPORTANT GOVERNANCE CRITERIA THROUGH PERCEPTION ANALYSIS

Following the same approach applied with socio-economic criteria, CoP members were asked to indicate the priority of each governance criterion for their MPAs. Where HP means “high Priority”, P “priority”, N “neutral”, LP “low priority” and NP “not a priority”. CoP’s opinion should be based on the following conditions: it helps the management process for conservation and/or for the planning of uses and activities (Table 7).

Only the governance criteria classified as HP or P should be ranked by the CoP members.

Table 7: Prioritization and ranking of the governance criteria

Priority	Ranking	GOVERNANCE CRITERIA	CRITERIA description/orientation
		Ecosystem based management approach	Ecosystem services are identified, assessed and incorporated to the management of the area
		Long term strategic adaptive management	Long term strategic management is adopted allowing a proactive, iterative and adaptive management. Lessons learned acquired along the different management cycles are being incorporated to management.
		Coherent management of the area	There is coherent coordination of international and sectoral policies and instruments in the area, and also of coastal-marine instruments to manage land-sea interactions. This coordination is articulated through inter-administrative and intra-administrative coordination mechanisms.
		Stakeholder participation	There is transparency, e.g. documents, and information are shared with the interested

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			parties, who participate in the management of the area and are satisfied with the participation process. The results of the participation are being incorporated into the management instruments. Public participation occurs in all management stages from the definition of objectives and the design of instruments to their implementation and evaluation.
		Equity	Clear objectives and social and cultural considerations are defined, adopted, and included in concrete measures. The measures adopted reduce conflicts between users and guarantee an equitable distribution of access to resources and areas, as well as the benefits that are generated.
		Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies	The objectives established for the area are developed through instruments (strategies, plans, measures,...), and those have an associated person in charge of their correct implementation.
		Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy	The plan sets out clear economic objectives related to the principles of a sustainable blue economy
		Sustainable fishing management	Sustainable fishing management is carried out: catches are below biological safety limits, sustainable reproduction is guaranteed, sizes and imposed closures are respected, continuous monitoring is carried out and adaptive management is carried out based on the best available knowledge.
		Climate change measures established	Measures are established to face the uncertainty scenarios generated by climate change. Mitigation and adaptation measures are included.
		Cross-border cooperation	Mechanisms for cross-border cooperation exist and are used to ensure good planning, monitoring and implementation of transnational issues.
		Decision making is based on best information knowledge available and	There are quality data and information accessible by the public and by the different administrations and sectors. All information and knowledge (including traditional knowledge) are considered in decision-making process in the area.

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		Strategic Environmental Assessment	There is an environmental strategic assessment when developing policies or tools to manage the area
		Monitoring evaluation	and Monitoring and evaluation of the objectives and management measures of the area are being carried out

STEP 5. CLASSIFICATION OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND GOVERNANCE CRITERIA IN ORDER TO ITS APPLICATION TO MSP AND THE DIFFERENT TYPES OF MPAs.

Based on the criteria list, it was requested to test site leaders to classify the application of every criterion to each case study, ranging from 0-Not applicable; + Partially; and ++ Fully applicable for both MSP and MPA process. To this end clear definition to each criterion was provided by UCA Team. The aim was to identify the scope of every criterion in terms of MPA and/or MSP: Is the criterion of relevance for MPAs, MSP or both taking in consideration the application of it for better-protected area management and MSP process?

During the process, new criteria can be added if test site leaders think there is something missing to their area, but a clear definition should be provided. Once the list of criteria presented here is based on a literature review made in Task 2.2 and Task 4.3, a brief explanation of why the criteria are being added is needed for justification purposes.

To analyse the relevance of the criteria for MPAs, it is important to consider the different types of MPA that vary greatly from no-take to sustainable use of MPA. To guide this process, it is used the definition proposed by IUCN, but adaptations to case studies must be considered when needed. Table 1 presents the IUCN definition for reference. Detailed information on IUCN categories can be found in Dudley (2008).

The following tables were delivered to apply this exercise. In Table 8, socio-economic criteria are those related to what exists in the area that could/should be taken into consideration in the process of establishing MPA or undertaking MSP. In Table 9, governance criteria are those that should exist in all MSP/MPA processes, so it is not possible to classify them according to their relevance or importance, but it is possible to indicate its actual implementation when designing the MPA or MSP.

Table 8: Relevance of criteria for the establishment of MPA or undertaking MSP. Where: 0 - Not applicable; + - Partially; and ++ - Fully.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC CRITERIA	Explanation/ proposed indicators	RELEVANCE (0 / + / ++)				
		MSP	IUCN MPA Category			OECMs
			Ia, Ib	II, III, IV	V, VI	

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Area with relevant traditional subsistence (or activity)						
Area as recreational, research and educational resource potential						
Area with important archaeological and historical sites						
Cultural sites of local importance (e.g., religious or other)						
Others...						

Table 9: Relevance of process criteria for the implementation when designing MPA or MSP.

GOVERNANCE CRITERIA	Explanation/ proposed indicators	RELEVANCE (0 / + / ++)				
		MSP	IUCN MPA Category			OECMs
			Ia, Ib	II, III, IV	V, VI	
Transparent decision making is ensured						
Engagement of relevant stakeholders ensured						
Gender equity and social diversity ensured						
Traditional knowledge equally included in the process						
Others						

As can be seen in previous Tables, to facilitate the work with CoP members, we have grouped the IUCN MPA categories in the followings three types of MPAs:

- MPA1. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas Ia and Ib are included. Therefore, MPA1 refers to marine protected areas that prioritize strict environmental protection above other uses.
- MPA2. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas II, III, and IV are included. Therefore, MPA2 refers to marine protected areas that prioritize the conservation of ecosystems or natural monuments, which can be achieved through active management.
- MPA3. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas V and VI are included. Therefore, MPA3 refers to marine protected areas of multiple uses where the goal is the sustainable use of natural resources.

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STEP 6. DATA COLLECTION PROCESS IN TEST SITES

The data collection process was structured based on the steps outlined above. In order to ensure transparency, it is crucial to emphasize that each case study employed distinct techniques when engaging with their CoP members. This step provides insights into the methodologies employed by each case study (Table 10).

Table 10: Information of the data collection process in Test Sites

NAME OF THE TEST SITE	
Provide a map and the following information here: Location: Name of MPA: Type of MPA: MPA Plan:	
About the process of CoP interaction to execute 4.1	Explain how was made the interaction with CoP members in your test site. Example: online/in person, number of respondents, type of stakeholders, etc.
Adjustments made to adapt the exercise to the test site	Explain how you adapted the methodology to the real conditions existing in your test site.
Main challenges faced in completing the exercise	Describe the difficulties you had when performance the exercise with your stakeholders
Main ecosystems	Why is your MPA valuable? What are the main ecosystems to protect?
Objectives of the MPA	What are the main objectives established to your MPA?
Main socio-economic characteristics of the MPA	What are the main characteristics in terms of social or economic conditions of your MPA?

STEP 7. DATA ANALYSIS

After the completion of the data collection phase, the following step was the organization and preparation of the gathered information for subsequent analyses. This process aimed to transform qualitative data into a format suitable for quantitative analysis while ensuring that the nuances and meaning of the original data were preserved.

To simplify the data analysis process, the qualitative responses were converted into a numerical format. Specifically, responses for criterion prioritization were categorized into five levels: "High priority," assigned a numerical value of 4; "Priority," a value of 3; "Neutral," a value of 2; "Low priority," a value of 1; and "Not a priority," a value of 0. The same approach was taken in relation to responses for criteria relevance for MSP and different types of MPA were categorized in three levels: "Fully," assigned a numerical value of 2; "Partially," a numerical value of 1 and "Not applicable," a numerical value of 0. This transformation allowed for the creation of a numerical dataset, therefore the application of various statistical analyses.

In addition, during the ranking section of the analysis, values equal to or higher than seven were excluded from consideration. By excluding these lower-ranking items, the analysis focused on identifying areas of divergence and discerning patterns among items with better ranked.

The data analysis procedures encompassed various statistical techniques, including descriptive statistics (e.g., average, standard deviation, and occurrence) and correlation analysis. These analyses aimed to uncover trends and relationships within the dataset, providing valuable insights into the research questions and objectives. It is important to note that each criterion was considered separately throughout the analysis. This approach ensures that the results for each criterion are distinct and independent. The analysis was conducted at two levels: firstly, at the level of each individual test site, and secondly, by aggregating the data from all six test sites. The results of this analysis can be found in the 'Results' section and are presented in two categories: one representing the analysis at the individual Test Site Leader level, and the other representing the aggregate results. These results have been further segmented into distinct sections, encompassing Governance Criteria, Socio-Economic Criteria, Ecosystem Services, as well as Criteria related to MSP and MPAs.

Correlation analysis

In this study, correlation analysis was employed to discern the relationship between criteria prioritization for various types of spatial management, namely MSP, MPA1, MPA2, MPA3 and OECMs. The analysis aimed to identify correlations between these criteria, shedding light on the distinct characteristics inherent in each spatial management approach. To achieve this, it was calculated the Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) for the following datasets:

- Socio-economic criteria relevance values for: MSP and MPA1, MSP and MPA2, MSP and MPA3, and MSP and OECMs.
- Governance criteria relevance values for: MSP and MPA1, MSP and MPA2, MSP and MPA3, and MSP and OECMs.

The Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) quantifies the strength of a linear relationship within the datasets, ranging from -1 to 1. Positive values indicate a tendency for both

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datasets to increase together, whereas negative values signify a tendency for one dataset to decrease as the other increases. A correlation coefficient of zero implies no apparent trend in either direction. This statistical measure provides valuable insights into the interconnections among the criteria sets.

The value of r is given by:

$$r = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}}, \text{ where}$$

- n is the set of data size;
- x_i, y_i are the individual value of the data set; and
- \bar{x}, \bar{y} are the average value of the data set.

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3. Results

In this section, we present the results of our study conducted across six test sites: Baltic Sea, Mediterranean, Atlantic (Azores), Atlantic (Cadiz Bay), Black Sea, and North Sea. Data collection took place from June 2nd to September 20th, by each test site leader analyzing the Relevance Criteria in relation to MSP and MPA processes.

It is important to highlight that in the case of the Baltic Sea test site, a distinct approach was adopted owing to its large-scale characteristics. To facilitate the execution of all exercises outlined in this research, a specific MPA in Poland was chosen, and consultations were conducted with a different group of stakeholders, not representing its Community of Practice (CoP). Henceforth, this selected MPA will be referred to as the Baltic MPA.

Results are presented separately for each test site and together, categorized into Socio-Economic and Governance criteria. This section provides insights into Socio-Economic Criteria, Governance Criteria, and Ecosystem Services.

To enhance the clarity of graphical and tabular presentations in the subsequent sections, it should be noted that the term 'CODE' refers to the unique identifiers corresponding to each socio-economic and governance criterion, as detailed in Table 11.

Table 11: List of criteria and codes

	Criteria	CODE
GOVERNANCE	Ecosystem based management approach	CG_1
	Long term strategic adaptive management	CG_2
	Coherence management of the area	CG_3
	Stakeholder participation	CG_4
	Equity	CG_5
	Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies	CG_6
	Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy	CG_7
	Sustainable fishing management	CG_8
	Climate change measures established	CG_9
	Cross-border cooperation	CG_10
	Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available	CG_11
	Strategic Environmental Assessment	CG_12
	Monitoring and evaluation	CG_13
SOCIO-ECONOMIC	Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities	CSE_1
	Area is important for fishery activity	CSE_2
	Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	CSE_3
	Area is important for shipping	CSE_4

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Area is important for dredging.	CSE_5
Area is important for locally-caught seafood	CSE_6
Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.	CSE_7
The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.	CSE_8
Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.	CSE_9
Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.	CSE_10
Area important for recreation and leisure.	CSE_11
Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.	CSE_12
Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc)	CSE_13
Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	CSE_14
Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.	CSE_15
Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.	CSE_16
Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.	CSE_17
Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes	CSE_18
Area is important for educational interest	CSE_19
An area that has high scientific interest.	CSE_20

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3.1. Relevance Criteria in relation to MSP and MPA process

3.1.1. Socio-economic Criteria

Figure 2: Prioritization Analysis: average values of Socio-economic criteria for MSP, MPA and OECMs. Values below 1 indicate the criterion is not applicable or relevant.

Table 12: Prioritization Analysis: value of socio-economic criteria in relation to MSP, MPA and OECMs. Color range varies from green (Fully applicable) to red (not relevant or applicable).

Code	MSP	SD	MPA 1	SD	MPA 2	SD	MPA 3	SD	OECMs	SD
CSE_1	1,86	0,38	0,50	0,84	0,67	0,82	1,00	0,58	1,00	0
CSE_2	2,00	0,00	0,50	0,84	1,17	0,41	1,71	0,49	1,50	0,548
CSE_3	2,00	0,00	0,67	1,03	1,67	0,52	1,86	0,38	1,33	0,516
CSE_4	2,00	0,00	0,83	0,75	0,67	0,52	1,29	0,76	1,17	0,408
CSE_5	2,00	0,00	0,67	1,03	0,83	0,98	1,00	0,82	1,00	0
CSE_6	1,86	0,38	0,50	0,84	1,00	0,00	1,57	0,53	1,67	0,516
CSE_7	1,14	0,69	1,67	0,52	1,67	0,52	1,43	0,79	1,50	0,548
CSE_8	1,43	0,79	0,83	0,75	1,17	0,41	1,29	0,76	1,17	0,408
CSE_9	1,29	0,49	0,83	0,41	1,50	0,55	1,43	0,79	1,17	0,408
CSE_10	1,43	0,53	0,50	0,55	1,00	0,00	1,43	0,79	1,17	0,408
CSE_11	1,57	0,53	0,83	0,98	1,50	0,55	1,57	0,79	1,33	0,516
CSE_12	0,71	0,76	1,67	0,52	1,50	0,55	1,43	0,79	1,00	0,894
CSE_13	1,14	0,69	1,17	0,75	1,50	0,55	1,43	0,79	0,83	0,753
CSE_14	0,29	0,49	0,67	0,82	1,33	0,82	1,29	0,95	0,50	0,548
CSE_15	1,14	0,69	2,00	0,00	2,00	0,00	1,86	0,38	1,33	0,516
CSE_16	1,43	0,79	0,67	0,82	0,83	0,75	1,00	1,00	1,33	0,516

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CSE_17	1,86	0,38	0,50	0,84	1,33	0,82	1,71	0,49	1,33	0,516
CSE_18	1,29	0,76	1,33	0,82	1,67	0,52	1,43	0,79	1,50	0,548
CSE_19	0,86	0,90	1,17	0,75	1,33	0,82	1,29	0,95	1,00	0,632
CSE_20	1,43	0,79	2,00	0,00	1,83	0,41	1,86	0,38	1,33	0,516

MPA1. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas Ia and Ib are included. Therefore, MPA1 refers to marine protected areas that prioritize strict environmental protection above other uses.

MPA2. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas II, III, and IV are included. Therefore, MPA2 refers to marine protected areas that prioritize the conservation of ecosystems or natural monuments, which can be achieved through active management.

MPA3. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas V and VI are included. Therefore, MPA3 refers to marine protected areas of multiple uses where the goal is the sustainable use of natural resources.

SD. Standard deviation

MSP. Maritime Spatial Planning

OECCMs. Other Effective Conservation Measures

According to Figure 2 and Table 12, the Test Site leaders of the six case studies have ranked as the most important socio-economic criteria to MSP, the followings:

CSE_2. Area is important for fishery activity

CSE_3. Area is important for the development of blue economy activities

CSE_4. Area is important for shipping

CSE_5. Area is important for dredging.

The above most ranked criteria have no deviation. The following three criteria were also highly ranked (1.86 from 2), but with a low standard deviation of 0.38:

CSE_1. Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities

CSE_6. Area is important for locally-caught seafood

CSE_17. Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.

Regarding MPA type 1, the most ranked (with no deviation) socio-economic criteria are as follows:

CSE_15. Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.

CSE_20. An area that has high scientific interest

To MPA type 2, the abovementioned criteria were also the most ranked, although there are others well ranked but with higher standard deviations.

MPA type 3 results shows a difference in the ranking compared to the other MPA types. In this case, also SE15 and SE20 were the most ranked, but to this it is added

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the SE3 “Area is important for the development of blue economy activities”. In this case can be observed that most of criteria are well ranked, but there is higher standard deviation in the responses.

The results obtained to OECMs (Other Effective Conservation Measures) shows a high degree of deviation, most of them higher than 0.5. The only two criteria ranked with 0 deviation were ranked as the lowest importance. They are:

CSE_1. Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities

CSE_5. Area is important for dredging.

Socioeconomic Criteria Relevance Analysis

Figure 3: Socio-economic criteria correlation analysis. R^2 is the coefficient the correlation varying from 0 to 1, where 0 means no relation and 1 full relation. R is the result of Pearson analysis, varying from – 1 to 1 and measures the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables.

The coefficient of correlation between MSP and MPA1 and MSP and MPA2 shows a negative relation, $r=-0.47$ and $r=-0.43$, respectively. In other words, the socio-economic criteria with more relevance for the establishment of the MSP are the less important when establishing MPA1 and MSP2, as presented in Figure 3.

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3.1.2. Governance Criteria

Figure 4: Prioritization Analysis: average values of governance criteria for MSP, MPA and OECMs. Values below 1 indicate the criterion is not applicable or relevant.

Table 13: Prioritization analysis: value of governance criteria in relation to MSP, MPA and OECMs. Color range varies from green (Fully applicable) to red (not relevant or applicable).

Code	MSP	SD	MPA 1	SD	MPA 2	SD	MPA 3	SD	OECMs	SD
CG_1	1,43	0,53	1,00	0,63	1,50	0,55	1,57	0,53	1,50	0,55
CG_2	1,71	0,49	1,50	0,55	1,67	0,52	1,43	0,79	1,17	0,41
CG_3	1,71	0,49	1,00	0,63	1,33	0,52	1,29	0,49	1,17	0,75
CG_4	2,00	0,00	1,00	0,89	1,33	0,52	1,57	0,53	1,67	0,52
CG_5	1,29	0,49	1,00	0,00	1,00	0,00	1,14	0,69	1,17	0,41
CG_6	1,71	0,49	1,50	0,84	1,67	0,52	1,29	0,76	1,67	0,52
CG_7	2,00	0,00	0,67	1,03	1,33	0,52	1,29	0,49	1,33	0,52
CG_8	2,00	0,00	0,50	0,84	1,50	0,55	1,57	0,53	1,33	0,52
CG_9	1,14	0,38	0,67	0,82	0,67	0,82	0,57	0,79	0,67	0,82
CG_10	1,57	0,53	1,17	0,41	1,50	0,55	1,29	0,49	1,33	0,52
CG_11	1,57	0,53	1,33	0,52	1,33	0,52	1,29	0,49	1,33	0,52
CG_12	2,00	0,00	1,00	0,89	1,33	0,82	1,57	0,79	1,33	0,52
CG_13	1,57	0,53	1,17	0,75	1,50	0,55	1,57	0,53	1,17	0,75

MPA1. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas Ia and Ib are included. Therefore, MPA1 refers to marine protected areas that prioritize strict environmental protection above other uses.

MPA2. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas II, III, and IV are included. Therefore, MPA2 refers to marine protected areas that prioritize the conservation of ecosystems or natural monuments, which can be achieved through active management.

MPA3. The IUCN categories of marine protected areas V and VI are included. Therefore, MPA3 refers to marine protected areas of multiple uses where the goal is the sustainable use of natural resources.

SD. Standard deviation

MSP. Maritime Spatial Planning

OECMs. Other Effective Conservation Measures

Most of the governance criteria were well ranked to MSP, although there are four criteria with the best ranking and no deviation in the responses (Figure 4 and Table 13). They are the followings:

- CG_4. Stakeholder participation
- CG_7. Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy
- CG_8. Sustainable fishing management
- CG_12. Strategic Environmental Assessment

Only two governance criteria were well ranked to MPA1 achieving a score of 1.5, although both have high degree of deviation (0.55 and 0.84) in the responses achieved. Those better ranked are:

- CG_2. Long term strategic adaptive management
- CG_6. Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies

In the case of MPA2, the governance criteria were better ranked but with high deviation degrees in the responses (more than 0.5). Better ranked criteria are:

- CG_1. Ecosystem based management approach
- CG_2. Long term strategic adaptive management
- CG_6. Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies
- CG_8. Sustainable fishing management
- CG_10. Cross-border cooperation
- CG_13. Monitoring and evaluation

The governance criteria were ranked like MPA3. They are ranked better than for MPA type 1 but with higher deviation degrees in the responses (more than 0.5 in most cases). To MPA3, the better ranked governance criteria are:

- CG_1. Ecosystem based management approach
- CG_4. Stakeholder participation
- CG_8. Sustainable fishing management
- CG_12. Strategic Environmental Assessment
- CG_13. Monitoring and evaluation

In the case of OECMs, the deviation degree in the responses is also high (more than 0.5 in most cases), although the criteria are well ranked (more than 1) expect criterion G9 "Climate change measures established", that has been also low ranked to every MPA type. In the case of OECMs, the best ranked governance criteria are:

- CG_1. Ecosystem based management approach
- CG_4. Stakeholder participation
- CG_6. Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies

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Governance Criteria Relevance Analysis

Figure 5: Governance criteria correlation analysis. R² is the coefficient the correlation varying from 0 to 1, where 0 means no relation and 1 full relation. *r* is the result of Pearson analysis, varying from -1 to 1 and measures the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables.

The coefficient of correlation between MSP and MPA1 shows a negative relation ($r=-0.12$). In other words, the criteria of governance more relevance for the establishment of the MSP are the less important when establishing MPA1. In terms of the result for the relation between MSP and MSP3, there is a higher correlation ($r=0.67$), meaning that the criteria considered as high priority for MSP are similar with those to established MPA3, as presented in Figure 5.

3.2. Results achieved in the Test Sites

Below, a condensed overview of the combined results from all test sites has been provided. This streamlined approach allows for a concise understanding of the collective findings. For a nuanced exploration of the specific outcomes at individual test sites, readers are encouraged to refer to the annex, where detailed data for each test site is elaborated upon.

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3.2.1. All Sea basins: The six test sites of MSP4BIO project

Figure 6: Tests Sites MSP4Bio Project.

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Table 14: MSP4Bio's Test Sites general information on ecosystems and activities.

REGION	ECOSYSTEM	ACTIVITIES	SCALE	INTERVIEWS
CADIZ BAY	Habitats: Meadows of three different seagrass species. Importance: Fish breeding and rearing, aquatic birds. Seafloor covered by seagrasses.	Industrial port operations, navigation, tourism, fishing, shellfish harvesting, aquaculture.	Local	8
NORTH SEA	Habitats: Sandbanks, gravel beds, sand mason worm aggregations.	Sand and gravel extraction, dredging, dumping of dredged materials, shipping, aquaculture, defense, future offshore wind energy generation, and potential passive fishing.	National (Belgium)	5
MEDITERRANEAN	Habitat: Productive pelagic environments. Importance: Two Ecologically or Biologically Important Marine Areas, two Important Marine Mammal Areas (IMMAs).	Shipping (one-third of Mediterranean traffic), exploring and demonstrating management solutions, scientific purposes, serves as a laboratory area for management practices.	International (Italy, France)	3
BLACK SEA	Habitats: Sandbanks, coastal lagoons, large shallow inlets and bays, reefs, annual vegetation of drift lines, vegetated sea cliffs, submerged or partially submerged sea caves. Importance: Natura 2000 protected species (2 fish, 2 marine mammals), second largest bird migratory route in Europe.	Fishing, coastal/beach tourism, navigation/marine traffic, military training, oil and gas extraction, nearby aquaculture.	National	3
BALTIC MPA	Habitats: Vistula Lagoon, shallow brackish water area. Importance: Migratory and nesting water birds, brackish and sea fish species spawning area.	Land reclamation, watercourse modifications, coastal defense, seabed restructuring, non-renewable energy generation, fishing, transport, urban development, waste management, tourism, research, education.	International (Poland, Russia)	3
AZORES	Habitats: Oceanic Island Importance: Hot spot of biodiversity, e.g., Deep black coral; other important species include Birds: Actitis macularius, Arenaria interpres, Bulweria bulwerii, Calidris alba, Calidris maritima, Calonectris borealis, Larus cachinnans, Larus	Limpet harvesting by artisanal fishermen.	Regional (Portugal)	1

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fuscus, *Larus hyperboreus*, *Larus marinus*, *Larus michahellis*, *Oceanodroma castro*, *Oceanodroma monteiroi*, *Onychoprion fuscatus*, *Puffinus baroli*, *Puffinus puffinus*, *Sterna dougallii*, *Sterna hirundo*.
Mammal: *Physeter macrocephalus*. Turtle: *Chelonia mydas*.

TOTAL

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3.2.2. Governance Criteria Analysis

Figure 7: Average of governance criteria prioritization of MSP4BIO's test sites. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Table 15: Average value of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - MSP4Bio's Test Sites.

Criterion	Criterion	Average priority	SD
CG_4	Stakeholder participation	3,57	0,50
CG_12	Strategic Environmental Assessment	3,55	0,41
CG_3	Coherence management of the area	3,47	0,30
CG_11	Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available	3,38	0,53
CG_1	Ecosystem based management approach	3,37	1,07
CG_8	Sustainable fishing management	3,31	0,57
CG_6	Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies	3,25	0,42
CG_2	Long term strategic adaptive management	3,16	1,44
CG_13	Monitoring and evaluation	2,97	0,39
CG_5	Equity	2,85	1,50
CG_7	Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy	2,85	0,91
CG_9	Climate change measures established	2,83	1,48
CG_10	Cross-border cooperation	2,00	1,04

The criterion **CG_5** has been evaluated as the highest priority criterion by all case sites in every sea basin except in Azores case site (See Figure 6 and Table 14). Similar situation occurs with **CG_6** and **CG_1**, scored as high priority by all case sites except in

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the Baltic MPA case site. **CG_11** is also scored as high priority by all case sites except the subcase of the entire Baltic, but at the same time it is being scored with the maximum punctuation by the MPA case within the Baltic. The most prioritized criteria for all Sea Basins are:

CG_5. Equity

CG_6. Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies

CG_1. Ecosystem based management approach

CG_11. Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available

CG_4. Stakeholder participation

On the other hand, the lowest scored governance criteria, although with high degrees of standard deviation, are:

CG_9. Climate change measures established

CG_2. Long term strategic adaptive management.

Figure 8: Governance criteria prioritization average per case site through a spider diagram.

Figure 8 shows two different situations. On one hand, in general there is slight differences in the prioritization of governance criteria among the case studies of Mediterranean, Black Sea and Cadiz Bay. For the two cases of the Baltic (the entire sea basin and the MPA within the Baltic) the situation is that there are high differences with to some of the criteria analysed. The Azores case study is an intermediate situation, with some differences with other case studies, but not as relevant as the situation observed to the Baltic cases.

The most prioritized criterion is **CG_5 “Equity”**, but it’s important to mention that it has the higher standard deviation among the respondents. Next criterion most prioritized is

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CG_6 “Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies” with a lower value of standard deviation.

Table 16: Governance criteria ranking and frequency of answers for rank – MSP4Bio’s Test Sites

Code	Criterion	Ranking Position	Occurrence
CG_1	Ecosystem based management approach	1	62,5%
CG_2	Long term strategic adaptive management	1 and 2	33,3%
CG_3	Coherence management of the area	1	27,3%
CG_4	Stakeholder participation	2, 3 and 4	22,2%
CG_5	Equity	1 and 2	11,1%
CG_6	Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies	2	23,5%
CG_7	Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy	3	30,0%
CG_8	Sustainable fishing management	3	35,7%
CG_9	Climate change measures established	3	30,0%
CG_10	Cross-border cooperation	11	30,0%
CG_11	Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available	2, 5 and 6	12,5%
CG_12	Strategic Environmental Assessment	3 and 8	25,0%
CG_13	Monitoring and evaluation	3	26,7%

When asked about ranking the most important governance criteria, CoP member of all sea basins ranked the following six at 1st and 2nd position:

CG_1 Ecosystem based management approach

CG_2 Long term strategic adaptive management

CG_3 Coherence management of the area

CG_5 Equity

CG_6 Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies

CG_4 Stakeholder participation

Among the previous most ranked governance criteria, the first and second present higher occurrence percentages.

The worst ranked criterion is the **CG_11 “Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available”** with a high occurrence percentage among case studies.

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3.2.3. Socio-Economic Criteria Analysis

Figure 9: Average of governance criteria prioritization of MSP4BIO's test sites. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Table 17: Average value of socio-economic criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - MSP4Bio's Test Sites.

CODE	Criterion	Average Priority	SD
CSE_20	An area that has high scientific interest.	3,19	0,54
CSE_7	Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.	3,09	1,08
CSE_8	The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.	2,89	1,14
CSE_11	Area important for recreation and leisure.	2,87	1,00
CSE_4	Area is important for shipping	2,85	1,00
CSE_3	Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	2,80	0,79
CSE_17	Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.	2,73	1,23
CSE_19	Area is important for educational interest	2,72	0,56
CSE_14	Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	2,66	0,81
CSE_9	Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which	2,65	1,22

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	is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.		
CSE_2	Area is important for fishery activity	2,59	1,17
CSE_15	Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.	2,53	1,10
CSE_13	Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc)	2,48	1,16
CSE_10	Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.	2,47	1,08
CSE_18	Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes	2,34	1,42
CSE_6	Area is important for locally-caught seafood	2,29	1,12
CSE_16	Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.	2,02	1,26
CSE_12	Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.	1,83	1,12
CSE_1	Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities	1,83	1,12
CSE_5	Area is important for dredging.	1,63	1,01

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Figure 10: Socio-economic criteria prioritization average per case site through a spider diagram.

The CoP members of all case studies have given the highest priority to the next five socio-economic criteria (Figure 9, 10, Table 17) with a standard deviation ranging from 0,54 to 1.14:

- CSE_20.** An area that has high scientific interest;
- CSE_7.** Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value;
- CSE_8.** The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality;
- CSE_11.** Area important for recreation and leisure;
- CSE_4.** Area is important for shipping.

On the other hand, the socio-economic criteria **5 “Area is important for dredging”** and **1 “Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities”**, were scored with the lowest priority for all the study cases.

Table 18: Table 51. Socio-economic criteria ranking and frequency of answers for rank – MSP4Bio’s Test Sites.

CODE	Criterion	Ranking Position	Frequency
CSE_1	Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities	2	36,4%
CSE_2	Area is important for fishery activity	2	25,0%
CSE_3	Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	1	46,7%
CSE_4	Area is important for shipping	2	18,8%
CSE_5	Area is important for dredging.	1	22,2%
CSE_6	Area is important for locally-caught seafood	1	33,3%

CSE_7	Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.	1	28,6%
CSE_8	The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.	3	16,7%
CSE_9	Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.	17	25,0%
CSE_10	Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.	3, 12, 13 and 15	18,2%
CSE_11	Area important for recreation and leisure.	2, 6 and 7	20,0%
CSE_12	Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.	2	26,7%
CSE_13	Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc)	3	30,8%
CSE_14	Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	8	23,1%
CSE_15	Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.	11	26,7%
CSE_16	Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.	1	25,0%
CSE_17	Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.	3	28,6%
CSE_18	Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes	4	30,8%
CSE_19	Area is important for educational interest	2 and 6	16,7%
CSE_20	An area that has high scientific interest.	2	33,3%

Asked about ranking the socio-economic criteria (Table 18), the CoP members of all case studies have ranked as most important the next six criteria:

CSE_3. Area is important for the development of blue economy activities;

CSE_5. Area is important for dredging;

CSE_6. Area is important for locally-caught seafood;

CSE_7. Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value;

CSE_16. Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.

All the above criteria were ranked in first position, being criterion 3 the one most commonly ranked with the higher importance, with a 47% of occurrence among the CoP members of all case studies.

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On the other hand, criterion **9 “Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment”** was ranked with the lowest importance. Criterion **10 “Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty “** was also scored low in the ranking if we sum the results obtained: 54.6% of respondents ranked it in 12, 13 and 15 position, although 18,2 % ranked it in the third position. Finally, criterion **15 “Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community”** was ranked in eleven position by 26.7% of the respondents.

The Table 19 displays the results obtained by correlating ecosystem services with various socio-economic criteria. These findings have been derived from the responses provided by the different Communities of Practitioners established within the case studies of the MSP4BIO project. No responses were received for the Baltic Sea case study.

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Table 19: Linking Ecosystem Services with socio-economic criteria in the Test Sites.

Ecosystem Services	ES examples	Criteria Related	Black Sea	Mediterranean	Cadiz	Azores	North Sea
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,	CSE_1, CSE_2 and CSE_3	CSE_1, CSE_2 and CSE_3	CSE_1, CSE_2 and CSE_3	CSE_1, CSE_2 and CSE_3	CSE 3	
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Controlling or preventing soil loss, regulating the flows of water in our environment and protecting people from extreme events (that can protect people)	CSE_8 and CSE_18	CSE_8 and CSE_18		CSE_8 and CSE_18		CSE_8 and CSE_18
Pest and disease control	Controlling pests, invasive species and diseases	CSE_2, CSE_8 and CSE_18	CSE_2 and CSE_8	CSE_2	CSE_2, CSE_8 and CSE_18		
Water conditions	Controlling the chemical quality of salt water enable human use and health.	CSE_8	CSE_8		CSE_8		
Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Decomposing or filtering wastes	CSE_8 and CSE_18	CSE_8 and CSE_18		CSE_8 and CSE_18		CSE_8
Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_8, CSE_9, CSE_10 and 18	CSE_3, CSE_6, and CSE_18		CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_8, CSE_9, CSE_10 and CSE_18		CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_8, CSE_9, CSE_10 and CSE_11
Regulation of soil quality	Ensuring the organic matter in our soils is maintained that maintains their characteristics necessary for human use	CSE_8			CSE_8		

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Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_8, CSE_9, CSE_10 and CSE_18	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_8, CSE_10 and CSE_18	CSE_1	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_8, CSE_9, CSE_10 and CSE_18		CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_9, and CSE_18
Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_9, CSE_10 and CSE_18	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_9, CSE_10 and CSE_18	CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_9, CSE_18	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_9, CSE_10 and CSE_18	CSE_3	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_10 and CSE_18
Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.	1, 3, 6, 8, 9, 10, and 18	1, 3, 6, 8, 9 and 10	CSE_8	1, 3, 6, 8, 10, and 18	CSE_3	
Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_8, CSE_9, CSE_10 and CSE_18	CSE_6 and CSE_10		CSE_1, CSE_3, CSE_6, CSE_8, CSE_10 and CSE_18		
Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)	CSE_4, CSE_5, CSE_16, CSE_17 and CSE_18	CSE_4, CSE_5, CSE_16 and CSE_17	CSE_4, CSE_5, CSE_16 and CSE_17	CSE_4, CSE_5, CSE_16, CSE_17 and CSE_18	CSE_4 and CSE_17	4, 5, 16, 17 and 18
Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)	1, 3, 9, 10 and 18	1, 3, 9 and 10		1, 3, 10 and 18		1, 3, 9 and 18

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Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Plants, fungi or algae that we can use for breeding	CSE_1, CSE_2 and CSE_3	CSE_1, CSE_2 and CSE_3		CSE_1, CSE_2 and CSE_3		
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Politization (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersal.	CSE_1, CSE_2, CSE_8, CSE_15 and CSE_18	CSE_1, CSE_2, CSE_8, CSE_15 and CSE_18	CSE_2, CSE_8, CSE_15 and CSE_18	CSE_1, CSE_2, CSE_8, CSE_15 and CSE_18	CSE_2, CSE_8 and CSE_15	CSE_1, CSE_2, CSE_8, CSE_15, CSE_18
Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Reducing smells or screening unsightly things	CSE_8	CSE_8		CSE_8		
Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulating our global climate and Regulating the physical quality of air for people	CSE_18	CSE_18	CSE_18	CSE_18		CSE_18
Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulating the physical quality of air for people (that affect people well-being or comfort)	CSE_8 and CSE_18	CSE_8 and CSE_18	CSE_8 and 18	CSE_8 and CSE_18		
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 19 and 20	6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	07 and 11	6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	7, 8, 11, 12, 13 and 15	6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20

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Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	The genetic information that is stored in wild animals that we can use	1, 2 and 3	1, 2 and 3		1, 2 and 3		
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem	7, 10, 12, 13, 14 and 15	7, 12, 13, 14 and 15	7, 12, 13, 14 and 15	7, 12, 13, 14 and 15		
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 19 and 20	6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19 and 20	7, 8, 11, 12, 13 and 15	6, 7, 8, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 19, 20
Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 20	8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 20	8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 20	8, 9, 12, 13, 14, 15 and 20		
Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	The ways the physical environment contribute to human (e.g., wind energy, ozone, sunlight)	1, 3 and 18		CSE_1 and CSE_3	CSE_1, CSE_3 and CSE_18		CSE_1, CSE_3 and CSE_18
Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g. caves; Natural e.g. whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	CSE_1, CSE_6, CSE_7, CSE_8, CSE_11, CSE_14, CSE_15, CSE_17 and CSE_18	CSE_1, CSE_6, CSE_7, CSE_8, CSE_11, CSE_14, CSE_15, CSE_17 and CSE_18	CSE_1, CSE_6, CSE_7, CSE_8, CSE_11, CSE_14, CSE_15, CSE_17 and CSE_18	CSE_1, CSE_6, CSE_7, CSE_8, CSE_11, CSE_14, CSE_15, CSE_17 and CSE_18	CSE_7, CSE_8, CSE_11, CSE_15 and CSE_17	CSE_1, CSE_6, CSE_7, CSE_8, CSE_11, CSE_12, CSE_14, CSE_15, CSE_17 and CSE_18

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Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Water used as: drinking water, material and no-drinking (e.g., cooling) and energy (e.g., tidal)	CSE_1, CSE_3 and CSE_18	CSE_3		CSE_1, CSE_3 and CSE_18	
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4. Discussion

One of the key objectives of this study is to establish a methodological framework for identifying socio-economic and governance criteria, providing a clear basis for prioritizing proposals such as new marine protected areas, revised MPA boundaries, reallocations, and more. This framework takes into account the MSP process, ensuring a comprehensive approach to decision-making with a higher emphasis in the EU legislation.

Through this comprehensive process, a final list of criteria was developed at project level, comprising 20 socio-economic criteria and 12 governance criteria. This list was collaboratively curated with relevant stakeholders and test site leaders in each test site of the MSP4Bio project. While this criteria list is robust, stemming from crucial legislations, agreements, and documents applicable across all case studies, the initial intention was for it to be preliminary and subject to expansion through proposals from Communities of Practice (CoP) and experts within each test site.

Interestingly, no new criteria proposals were received after the completion of the exercises. This absence of proposals could be attributed to two possible reasons. Firstly, it is plausible that the existing criteria comprehensively encompass all the diverse realities analysed by the project. Alternatively, it may indicate the necessity for a targeted exercise specifically designed to analyse and propose new criteria, thereby enhancing the methodology. Further investigation is required to discern the underlying cause and to refine the methodology for future applications. In reference to the study's objective of identifying Ecosystem Services (ES) and their societal value associated with MPAs, it is crucial to note that utilizing the ES provided by the Common International Classification of ES under the "Group" column has yielded positive outcomes. Expanding beyond the "Group" column would result in a longer and more specific list of ES, making it more challenging to work with and potentially leading to misunderstandings, necessitating further explanations to stakeholders. Restricting the analysis to the "Group" column simplifies understanding for stakeholders while still enabling the derivation of pertinent conclusions. In this sense, it is also important to mention that the North Sea Test site has also adjusted the different types of ecosystem services to make it easier for their CoP members to go through the exercise. The test site has used the nomenclature used in the work of Custodio et al., (2022).

A more in-depth analysis of the results is presented in this section, and are organized into the following subsections: i) the relationship between MSP, MPA, and OECMs; ii) governance criteria; iii) socio-economic criteria; and, finally; iv) the most relevant ecosystem services and their relationship with socio-economic criteria. The main findings are discussed below.

4.1. The relationship between MSP, MPA and OECMs

Upon analyzing Table 12 and 13, distinct correlations have come to light. There is a robust positive correlation between MSP and MPA3, whereas MSP exhibits an inverse relationship with both MPA1 and MPA2. This contrasting correlation increases along with the uses of restriction towards conservation goals inherent to the different types of the IUCN MPAs.

Furthermore, Pearson analyses conducted (MSP and MPA1, MSP and MPA2, MSP and MPA3, and MSP and OECMs) give more material to assess the commonalities and divergencies between the different spatial management methods, as can be seen in Figures 3 and 5. For example, in Figure 3, it revealed a consistent negative correlation between MSP and MPA1 and MPA2 related to socio-economic criteria. Additionally, a negative correlation is also observed between MSP and MPA1 in governance criteria Figure 5. Therefore, the analysis of socio-economic and governance criteria has shown a notable lack of a significant relationship between MSP and MPA1 and MPA2, highlighting a distinct disparity in their application and goals. These findings underscore the necessity for a different approach and heightened attention when dealing with these specific conservation approaches within MSP plans.

On the other hand, the governance criteria exhibited a high correlation between MSP and MPA3, suggesting a striking similarity in the approaches employed in these spatial management practices. In terms of the socio-economic criteria, the analysis indicate that the sustainable development is more in evidence in both MSP and MPA3 spatial management approaches, even with different scale of application (MPA usually more locally and MSP National/regional). Another point that stands out in the socio-economic analysis between MSP and MPA is the difference in the results obtained to MSP and MPA3 relies on Criteria 12 “Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value”; Criteria 14 “Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)”, and Criteria 19 “Area is important for educational interest ” with all of them scoring much higher in MPA3. These results indicate that non-monetary social values are more willing to be taken into consideration in a small-scale approach like a MPA process than in a larger one such as MSP.

These findings come to add to the discussion on the connection of the integration and connection of MSP and MPA (e.g. Trouillet and Jay (2021); Vaughan and Agardy (2020).) through socio-economic and governance criteria. Moreover, as a novelty, the present work develops such connections between MSP and the different types of MPA giving a new perspective to be worked on since the relevance of governance and socio-economic criteria changes significantly among the different types of MPA, therefore attention to these nuances should be considered.

4.2. Governance criteria

It is evident that while the governance criteria showed a consistent pattern of standardization across the case studies, this uniformity derives from the general framework provided by the European Union. Despite the enormous differences in the socioecological dynamics of each sea basin, a common regulatory framework leads to a homogenization in prioritizing governance-related criteria.

In this sense, the criterion related to the "Coherence management of the area" (CG_3) is the one that presents the most homogeneous data among all the case studies, presenting values higher than 3.5 in terms of prioritization of the criterion in all the case studies except for the North Sea. It is followed by three other criteria that also present little disparity in terms of the valuation given in the different case studies: "Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies" (CG_6), "Strategic Environmental Assessment" (CG_12) and "Monitoring and evaluation" (CG_13).

The above criteria are generic and strategic for any MSP process, as well as for the designation or management of a Marine Protected Area. Therefore, the internalization by the countries of some of the characteristics that should be found in an MSP process, such as those indicated in the UNESCO MSP guide, is evident (Ehler, C. and Douvère, F., 2009). It presents, among the steps of an MSP process, the implementation of strategic planning, as well as the need for adaptive management through monitoring and feedback.

Moreover, the criteria on the "Coherence management of the area" (CG_3) and the generation of "Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies" (CG_6) are common to most of the case studies due to the practicality and logic of managing a given area.

Despite the similarities in the prioritization of governance criteria, there are some that stand out in particular case studies.

Firstly, the criterion on "Ecosystem Based Management approach" (CG_1) stands out in terms of prioritization in the Bay of Cadiz, Mediterranean and Black Sea. In these regions, this approach is particularly important due to the unique ecological characteristics and the high level of human activity (Micheli et al., 2013). Marine Spatial Planning and the creation of Marine Protected Areas are essential tools for implementing EBM processes, in which they can be obtained by promoting sustainable tourism, recreational activities, and other non-extractive uses of marine resources (Douvère, 2008).

In the Mediterranean, it is worth highlighting the progress made in the MSP with an ecosystem-based management approach (Manea et al., 2020). This document also establishes a set of area-based management tools for marine protected areas and marine conservation. Therefore, it can be seen how this test site is supported by

guidance documents to advance in the creation or management of ecosystem-based MPAs.

The similarities in the valuation of the aforementioned criterion coincide with those obtained for "Sustainable fishing management" (CG_8), with outstanding values for the aforementioned case studies. This shows the importance of economic activities in these regions, especially fishing, the existing problems and the need to establish mechanisms for sustainable fisheries based on the ecosystem (Santos et al., 2015).

The criterion related to "Climate change measures established" (CG_9), although obtaining high prioritization values in all the test sites, stands out especially in the case studies of the Bay of Cadiz and the Mediterranean. Climate change is causing sea levels to rise globally, and this is particularly relevant in the Bay of Cadiz and the Mediterranean region, where higher sea levels is leading to coastal erosion, increased flooding, and the intrusion of saltwater into freshwater aquifers (UNEP/MAP and Plan Bleu, 2020). Specifically, there is evidence that the Mediterranean is getting warmer 20% faster than the global trend (MedECC, 2020). All this leads to the fact that the stakeholders in these case studies observe the consequences of climate change more directly and hence to the prioritization of this criterion in the formulation of the MPAs. Also, in the cases of the marine protected areas in Poland and Cádiz, the priority given to taking measures to combat climate change is maximal. This may be due to the characteristics of both areas, which are characterized by the presence of shallow-water ecosystems that are more susceptible to climate change (López Herrera et al., 2022; Bilkovic et al., 2009). In the case of the Pelagos Sanctuary (Mediterranean), climate change is also of the utmost priority. This MPA is heavily frequented by cetaceans. Therefore, the priority assigned may be related to the sensitivity of these marine mammals to climate change (Elliott, W. and Simmonds, M. 2007).

Moreover, climate change is a recurring issue in the various policies and agreements applicable to the test sites; indeed, the European Green Deal (EGD) aims to make Europe climate-neutral by 2050. However, governance criterion 9, related to the establishment of measures to combat it, has been assessed as of very low importance for all types of marine protected areas, OEMCs, and even for the MSP (Table 11). This situation may be explained by the difficulty of adopting measures to combat the local effects of global change, the urgency of other issues with more short-term oriented results (it is not a matter on local political agendas), or even the lack of public understanding on what climate change adaptation entails and training for technicians and managers to promote better adaptation or resilience to changes induced by climate change.

On the other hand, the case studies of the Azores and the North Sea are the ones that have given very low priority to issues related to climate change. In the first case, it is an island of volcanic origin, characterised by its limited continental shelf, high average altitude, and its location in the middle of the Atlantic Ocean. These characteristics could

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make its depth-water ecosystems less sensitive in the short term to the effects of climate change compared to the case of Cádiz which has shallow water and sea level rise is already a fact (Vázquez Pinillos and Marchena Gómez, 2021), although scientific evidence on Azores vulnerability to climate change is lacking (Telmo et al., 2020; ICES, 2023). Regarding the North Sea, recent studies show that the benthic ecosystems characterising the MPA are under greater pressure from climate change (Weinert et al., 2021; Dulvy et al., 2008). However, it is possible that the activities taking place in the area (dredging, aquaculture, etc.) may have a lower vulnerability to the effects of climate change, which could explain a lower perception of its impact by the consulted stakeholders.

Another criterion that stands out due to the divergence of responses in the different case studies is the "Cross-border cooperation" criterion (G10), which is highly valued in the Black Sea test site. This is evident from the high number of countries whose coasts are part of the Black Sea, and therefore maritime uses and activities are conditioned by neighbouring countries. This is reflected in research which shows that cross-border cooperation in the Black Sea is difficult to achieve due to the existing legislative differences (Tatenhove, J. et al., 2014). However, recently, cross-border cooperation in MSP has advanced notably for Bulgaria and Romania, as evidenced by initiatives such as the EU MS, MARSPLAN-BS I and II projects, and MSFD for MPAs. On the contrary, transboundary cooperation in MSP and MPAs has proven to be challenging. This difficulty arises primarily because many countries involved are not EU Member States (Văidianu et al., 2020). Additionally, the current geopolitical scenario, including the conflict between Ukraine and Russia, further complicates international collaboration in this domain.

In the case of the Baltic Sea, although it is an area with high international interactions between maritime uses and activities, such a high prioritization of the aforementioned criterion has not been obtained. This may be due to the fact that it is a criterion that has already been overcome in the Baltic, as confirmed by the different publications and good practices on cross-border cooperation in the region (Studzieniecki, 2016; Gustafsson et al., 2018; Janßen et al., 2018), and that the test site consists of a specific area.

4.3. Socio-economic criteria

Built upon the work of Withouck et al. (2023), which identified existing criteria lists used in conservation and restoration initiatives, the final socio-economic list of criteria is divided into four categories (ANNEX II): i) Blue Economy; ii) Culture; iii) Human Well-being; and iv) Education and Science.

Although it does not encompass all blue sector activities, the Blue Economy category includes six criteria, with fishery, shipping, and dredging sectors highlighted based on various directives, instructions, and international documents (ANNEX I). Additionally,

two criteria in this category have broader concepts, addressing different maritime sectors:

- "Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to non-traditional activities."
- "Area is important for the development of blue economy activities."

Criteria related to more traditional activities are included in the socio-economic criteria list under the Human Well-being category. This approach ensures the inclusion of diverse economic uses and activities, which are highlighted when analyzed in detail for each type of management approach (Table 12).

For example, Table 12 shows the prioritization of criteria across different management scenarios:

- **Column MSP:** Criteria related to economic activities are prioritized (CSE_1 to CSE_6).
- **Column MPA 1:** The same criteria (CSE_1 to CSE_6) appear as the least priority.
- **Columns MPA 2 and MPA 3:** A mix of prioritization is observed between CSE_1 to CSE_6, with MPA 3 being more flexible regarding criteria related to economic activities with a higher potential for environmental impact (e.g., dredging).

By categorizing and prioritizing the criteria in this manner, it is ensured that diverse economic uses and activities of different scales are appropriately represented within the socio-economic framework. However, it is important to emphasize that the framework is a guide for the final user, and although it shows some tendencies, it must be adapted and discussed among stakeholders of an area.

As mentioned before, in analysing the governance criteria across the six test sites, it was observed a consistent pattern of standardization. However, the socio-economic criteria analysis revealed higher standard deviation values and lower prioritization values among the test sites. This discrepancy can be attributed to the fact that while the test sites share a common marine governance framework, the socio-economic aspects are more site-oriented, aligning with national and local objectives, and the ecosystem under protection.

Despite the diversity among the test sites, seven criteria stood out in the overall assessment: "Area is important for the development of blue economy activities" (SE_C 3); "Area is important for shipping" (SE_C 4); "Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value" (SE_C 7); "Area is important for recreation and leisure" (SE_C 11); "Area is important with the occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community" (SE_C 14); "Area is important for educational interest" (SE_C 19); and "An area that has high scientific interest" (SE_C 20). The first two criteria are economically focused, while the

remaining five are more socially oriented, in line with the results for ecosystem services, that will be discussed further in the report.

Notably, SE_C 20 received the highest priority scores across all test sites, exceeding the value of 3 in each case. This criterion is closely related to the governance criterion "monitoring and evaluation" (G13), which also ranked high among the test sites, emphasizing the crucial role of these criteria in the effectiveness of management plans for protected areas. The relevance of these criteria is magnified due to the challenges posed by rapidly changing environments, driven by both local and global stressors such as climate change (Fox et al., 2012; Rilov et al., 2020), being critical for ecosystem recognizing as vulnerable as such shallow-waters (Bay of Cadiz test Site and Baltic MPA test site) and marine-mammals (NorthWestern Mediterranean test site) (López Herrera et al., 2022; Bilkovic et al., 2009; Elliott, W. and Simmonds, M. 2007).

The second prominent socio-economic criterion is "Area is important for the development of blue economy activities" (C_SE 3). As illustrated in Table 14, except for the MPA in the Azores test site, all MPAs assessed exhibited a variety of uses within the protected area as such, aquaculture, fishing, shipping lanes, renewable energy, oil and gas, tourism, etc.

Significantly, the criterion related to the Blue Economy demonstrated its importance, evidenced by its high priority value of 2.80, low standard deviation (0.79), and superior ranking (18.8% ranked as first) within the assessment. This observation gains particular significance within the context of MPAs, highlighting their role in accommodating diverse uses while theoretically promoting sustainable development. These findings are crucial, as outlined in Table 12, where the intricate relationship between different criteria and various spatial management strategies (MSP, MPA, and OECMs) is explored. The alignment of them fostering a balanced and sustainable ecosystem, as discussed in the context of "MSP, MPA, and OECMs."

4.4. The ecosystem services with most social value and existing relations with socio-economic and governance criteria.

The results of the exercise conducted by the stakeholders who are part of the Communities of Practice (CoPs) in the five analyzed cases **demonstrate that the ES with most social value are the regulatory services that MPAs provide for human well-being.**

The high importance attributed to regulatory services correlates with the attention given to them in the definition of a marine protected area (MPA), understood as 'marine space designated and effectively managed to protect marine ecosystems, processes, habitats, and species, which can contribute to the restoration and replenishment of resources for social, economic, and cultural enrichment' (Reuchlin-Hugenholts and Mackenzie, 2015). According to this definition, an MPA must protect the natural elements that provide the capacity of the protected area to deliver regulatory ecosystem services. This natural

foundation will enable the MPA to generate resources that local society uses for its well-being. In this regard, **the idea is that MPAs should emphasize the protection of the natural or ecosystem-based foundation that supports the socio-ecosystem of which the marine area is a part** (Concepción Marcos et al., 2021; Barragán et al., 2020; De Andrés et al., 2018; Rees et al., 2018). This idea is important because in the absence of a society making activities and therefore introducing pressures in the area, protecting it would be pointless, hence **the need to view MPAs as spaces that are part of a larger socioecosystem** (De Juan, S. et al., 2023).

The **above conclusion positively correlates with the high rating obtained for the governance criterion called 'ecosystem-based management approach'** in the case studies of the Mediterranean, Bay of Cadiz, Black Sea. Indeed, ecosystem-based management is at the core of the theoretical application of MPAs (Browman et al., 2004; Halpern et al., 2010; Long et al., 2015) and MSP It implies a holistic-integrated approach where all processes are considered, including those in which people intervene; this carries us again to the idea of allocating humans as an integral part of the socio ecosystem in which the MPA is a part.

The second finding that can be gleaned from the analysis is that **the cultural services provided by MPAs are equally or even more important than provisioning services**. This makes sense when considering that provisioning services often involve the extraction of resources from the system, except in cases where resources are used renewably, and this can sometimes contradict the idea of protecting a marine area, so these uses would be more limited. Indeed, fisheries are often displaced by MPAs that usually support other activities, deemed less extractive, to maintain the livelihoods of neighbouring communities (Erskine et al., 2021).

In fact, in four of the five protected MPAs analyzed (excluding the Black Sea MPA), stakeholders have highlighted the importance of the cultural services provided by their MPAs. In contrast, only a few provisioning ecosystem services have been rated as important in the studied MPAs.

It is also noteworthy in the case of the North Sea the service 'Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials, or energy,' which in this case relates to the importance of offshore wind energy in the area. In the case of the Pelagos Sanctuary in the Mediterranean, the service 'Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials, or energy' is also highlighted. The case of the Azores stands out, where no importance is given to any provisioning service, even though the marine protected area is used for limpet harvesting. On the contrary, several cultural services were highlighted in the Azores.

The results obtained from the cross-referencing of ecosystem services with socio-economic criteria (Table 19) appear to support the aforementioned ideas. Indeed, **the ecosystem services that fulfil the most socio-economic criteria are those related to cultural services**. As an example, the service 'Intellectual and representative

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interactions with the environment (abiotic and natural)” has been related by CoPs members to 13 of the 20 socio-economic criteria studied. It should not be forgotten that every socio-economic criterion has been extracted from the main policies, regulations, documents, or international agreements applicable to European countries (See Table 1). Taking this into consideration, the results obtained support the idea that **marine protected areas fulfil a role strongly related to the socio-cultural well-being of the population**. This for sure has implications for the management of these areas. Indeed, there is a growing literature supporting the idea that the MPAs should use a diverse locally appropriate protection levels to achieve positive biodiversity outcomes (Andradi-Brown et al., 2023; Halik et al., 2018). This approach defends that partially protected MPAs can offer effective and equitable pathways for biodiversity conservation if tailored to local context (Andradi-Brown et al., 2023). If this approach is followed, we would be talking about MPAs type 3 (IUCN categories V and VI).

5. Conclusions

While this methodology developed for the identification of the socio-economic and governance criteria and its application exhibit several limitations, which will be elaborated upon later in this section, certain identified outcomes prove to be immensely valuable for the ongoing development of the MSP4Bio project as well as for broader discussions on MSP and MPA initiatives.

The analysis of diverse test sites, each characterized by unique ecosystems and political approaches, revealed significant similarities. In terms of the governance criteria analysis, four criteria emerged ("Coherence management of the area", "Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies", "Strategic Environmental Assessment", and "Monitoring and evaluation"), and a consistent standardization pattern among the criteria across all case studies stood out. This consistent pattern strongly suggests the influence of the general ocean governance framework established by the European Union. To strengthen our findings, it is imperative to extend this methodology beyond the test sites and later the EU borders, thus providing further validation.

In the evaluation of socio-economic criteria, seven distinct criteria ("Area is important for educational interest", "An area that has high scientific interest", "Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value", "The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality", "Area is important for the development of blue economy activities", "Area is important for shipping", and "Area important for recreation and leisure") stood out in the comprehensive assessment. Despite the site-specific nature of socio-economic aspects, which are linked with national and local objectives, as well as the protected ecosystem, the result shows that the services offered by the ecosystem outweigh the specific ecosystem itself, since common prioritization were identified in the six different test sites. This finding is particularly significant, especially when considering marine protected areas categorized as MPA3, as different ecosystems can provide identical services. This insight emphasizes the importance of focusing on the services rendered by ecosystems, and in other words, the people who use these services.

Furthermore, the results from diverse case studies, underscore the significance of climate change, albeit with varying degrees of urgency. The findings indicate that climate change is universally recognized as a crucial issue. However, the urgency in addressing it varies based on the distinct vulnerabilities of ecosystems, prevailing perceptions, and the nature of activities directly or indirectly linked to these ecosystems. This nuanced understanding highlights the necessity for tailored approaches that consider these diverse factors, ensuring effective strategies in mitigating the impact of climate change on marine ecosystems. In this context, the work developed in Task 3.3 and the work that will be carried out in Task 4.3 of the MSP4Bio Project are of fundamental relevance.

It is essential to emphasize that the results presented in this study do not intend to capture the entirety of the most critical socio-economic and governance criteria or the utmost valuable ecosystem services specific to each test site region. Instead, the aim of

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this research was to provide a structured approach for examining these multifaceted aspects within the context of spatial planning, focusing on marine spatial planning and marine protected areas. In this way, allowing the identification of synergies between both processes.

The methodology employed here has showcased its potential in seamlessly integrating the socio-economic dimension with the environmental aspect, primarily through its focus on ecosystem services. This integration is instrumental in aiding policymakers and stakeholders to recognize and visualize the interdependence between these dimensions—a critical factor for promoting sustainable development and fostering cooperation among stakeholders.

In this regard, our methodology stands as a valuable tool in addressing this critical gap. By spotlighting the interplay between socio-economic factors and ecosystem services, it equips decision-makers with a more comprehensive understanding of the consequences of their choices, thereby enabling more informed, just and sustainable spatial management.

Moreover, it's important to recognize that neither the socio-economic dynamics nor the ecological dynamics are static. Understanding these changes over time and adapting our approach to manage and create new areas is of paramount importance. Our methodology not only provides a snapshot of the current state but also offers a framework for ongoing assessment and adaptation to evolving circumstances, since the criteria can be (and will be) associated to a indicator allowing keeping tracking of the evolvement of the area (Task 4.3. of MSP4BIO Project).

Furthermore, this methodology plays a pivotal role in providing material for trade-off discussions in task 4.3 of the MSP4BIO project. It offers a structured framework for assessing the trade-offs and synergies between different socio-economic criteria and ecosystem services, helping stakeholders make informed decisions that balances socio-economic development with environmental conservation. Since the identification of the main socio-economic criteria and ecosystem services allows a more oriented selection of indicators to be mapped and integrated in the process of negotiation.

Recognizing the inherent limitations of our methodology developed to identify the clear criteria for prioritizing new spatial management areas in a more coherent, effective and integrating the social dimension, we acknowledge the need for further enhancements. In the last section of this report, titled "Final Remarks," we provide a comprehensive list of actions and processes that should be integrated into future applications of this methodology to refine and validate its outcome (socio-economic and governance criteria, and valuation of ecosystem services) which is the main goal of this report. These refinements are intended to bolster the robustness and efficacy of the outcomes generated, addressing the challenges posed by time restrictions and ensuring a more comprehensive and reliable assessment.

6. Final remarks (Final remarks regarding Socio-economic criteria and their ecosystem services and Trade-off analysis)

Due to the novelty of the methodological approach and the time constraints, the enhancement of the methodology primarily evolved through a 'learning-by-doing' approach. It is important to acknowledge that certain aspects could not be fully addressed within the scope of this final report, but it is imperative to recognize their significance and plan for their integration into the methodology in future iterations. Below some of these points are presented.

1. Allocate a more extended timeframe for thorough explanation and training sessions with the ones in charge to execute apply the method. This will allow for a deeper understanding of the methodology and its applications, enabling more effective implementation and standardization of the results.
2. Implement an additional workshop dedicated to the validation of results for each test site. This step will enhance the credibility and accuracy of the findings by involving key stakeholders in the review and verification process. Moreover, this would also allow a discussion between stakeholders to find a common path, improving the final outcome of the methodology. This additional workshop could be avoided if the methodology can be done by an application (dashboard or other) in which the stakeholders can introduce their thoughts and at the end and immediate feedback so they can discuss and validate the results achieved.
 - a. Observation: It is important to mention that inside the MSP4BIO project there will be a validation workshop on the full framework proposed which this work fits in in the near future.
3. Develop a map illustrating the ecosystem services of the analyzed area. This visual representation helps understanding and contextualizing the ecological dynamics within the region under study, therefore leading to a better outcome.
 - a. Observation: Inside the MSP4BIO project this will be done in the Task 4.3. related to trade-off.
4. Development of indicators for the socio-economic and governance criteria. This would support the assessment of the process as a whole.
5. Monitoring and assessment of the ecosystem providing the ecosystem services that are connected to the socio-economic criteria listed as high priority, closing the cycle.
6. The scales of the test site also play a very important role in the results of this study. Have a clear understanding of how the integration of results might affect the site-specific application of the outcomes is relevant to future applications the outcomes here presented.
7. Some set criteria to define OECM areas are fundamental for the execution of the exercise;

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Marine ecosystem services valuation plays a pivotal role in the tradeoff assessment integral to marine spatial planning (MSP) and the establishment of marine protected areas (MPAs). By making the quantitative analysis on the economic, ecological, and societal benefits derived from marine ecosystems, valuation enables decision-makers to make informed choices. It provides a scientific foundation for evaluating the trade-offs between various human activities, conservation efforts, and sustainable resource use within marine environments. Ultimately, this approach aids in optimizing the allocation of marine resources, promoting ecological integrity, and ensuring the long-term well-being of both marine ecosystems and the communities dependent on them.

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8. Annexes

ANNEX I. Documents analysed to identify socio-economic criteria

Geographic scale	Institution/Convention	Institution type	sectoral/conservation related (if sectoral: specify)	Name source
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	Birds Directive Article 4
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	Habitats Directive Annex III
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	Hab. 97/2 rev. 4 18/11/97
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	COMMISSION DECISION (EU) 2017/848 of 17 May 2017 laying down criteria and methodological standards on good environmental status of marine waters and specifications and standardised methods for monitoring and assessment, and repealing Decision 2010/477/EU (p. 72-73)
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	MSFD Annex III Indicative list of

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				characteristics, pressures and impacts (Table 1)
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	WFD Annex V definitions ecological status
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	COM DEC 2017/848/EU
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	Reporting format Article 12 (pdf) (Annex B box 2-5)
European level	EU	IGO	conservation	Reporting format Article 17 (pdf) (Annex C first three listed parameters)
European level	EU	IGO	restoration	Nature Restoration Law Article 11 (2)
European level	EU	IGO	sectoral:fishing	Common Fisheries Policy Article 8
International level	UNESCO	institution broader mandate	both (conservation/development/logistics support)	Criteria WNBR Statutory Framework Art.4
International level	UNESCO	institution broader mandate	both (cultural and natural heritage)	The Criteria for Selection to be included on the World Heritage List, sites must be of outstanding universal

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				value and meet at least one out of ten selection criteria.
International level	CBD	convention	conservation	Annex I SCIENTIFIC CRITERIA FOR IDENTIFYING ECOLOGICALLY OR BIOLOGICALLY SIGNIFICANT MARINE AREAS IN NEED OF PROTECTION IN OPEN-OCEAN WATERS AND DEEP-SEA HABITATS CBD Decision IX/20)
International level	Ramsar	convention	conservation	The Ramsar Sites Criteria: The nine criteria for identifying Wetlands of International Importance
International level	UNCLOS	convention	conservation	Draft agreement under the UNCLOS on the conservation and sustainable use of marine

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biological
diversity of
areas beyond
national
jurisdiction,
Annex 1

International level	GEO BON	global network	conservation	EBV classes and names
International level	BirdLife International	NGO	conservation	Guidelines for the application of the IBA criteria Final version, July 2020
International level	IUCN	NGO	conservation	IMMA Selection Criteria
International level	IUCN	NGO	conservation	A Global Standard for the Identification of Key Biodiversity Areas
International level	IUCN	NGO	conservation	IUCN Red List Categories and Criteria
International level	IUCN	NGO	conservation	IUCN Red List of Ecosystems Criteria
International level	UNESCO O-IOC	ocean institution	conservation	Methodology for the GEF Transboundary Waters Assessment Programme: ecological criteria listed on p. 1
International level	UNESCO O-IOC	ocean institution	conservation	EOV specification

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International level	SER	institution on broader mandate	restoration	International Standards for the Practice of Ecological Restoration - Including Principles and Key Concepts (p.47)
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International level	FAO	institution on broader mandate	sectoral:fishing	INTERNATIONAL GUIDELINES FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF DEEP-SEA FISHERIES IN THE HIGH SEAS, p. 8: 5.2 Identifying vulnerable marine ecosystems and assessing significant adverse impacts
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International level	IMO	ocean institution	sectoral:shipping	Annex Resolution A.982(24), Section 4: ECOLOGICAL, SOCIO-ECONOMIC, OR SCIENTIFIC CRITERIA FOR THE IDENTIFICATION OF A PARTICULARLY SENSITIVE
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				SEA AREA
International level	IMO	ocean institution	shipping	ANNEX 1 GUIDELINES FOR THE DESIGNATION OF SPECIAL AREAS UNDER MARPOL 73/78 (2001 GUIDELINES FOR THE DESIGNATION OF SPECIAL AREAS UNDER MARPOL 73/78 AND GUIDELINES FOR THE IDENTIFICATION AND DESIGNATION OF PARTICULARLY SENSITIVE SEA AREAS)
International level	IMO	ocean institution	shipping	Appendix III - Criteria and procedures for designation of SOx emission control areas (Regulation 14)
Mix (but all are within EU)	DEVOTES	science project	conservation	A Catalogue of Marine Biodiversity

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Indicators

Regional Level (Baltic Sea)	HELCO M	IGO	conservation	Selection Criteria – HELCOM MPAs
Regional Level (Black Sea)	BlackSea C	IGO	conservation	ANNEX 4 List of Species Whose Exploitation Should be Regulated by the Black Sea Biodiversity and Landscape Conservation Protocol (criteria 1-6)
Regional Level (Black Sea, Mediterranean Sea and Contiguous Atlantic Area)	ACCOBA MS	IGO	conservation	"INPUTS TO THE ACCOBAMS ONGOING EFFORT TO MAP HUMAN THREATS ON CETACEANS IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AND BLACK SEAS", p. 3
Regional Level (Mediterranean Sea)	SPA/RA C	IGO	conservation	Annex I Common criteria for the choice of Protected Marine and Coastal Areas that could be included in SPAMI list

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Regional Level (Mediterranean Sea)	OCEANA	NGO	sectoral:fishing	Towards A Mediterranean Network of EFHs Annex 2: Selection of areas to be included in the Mediterranean network of EFH
Regional Level (Northeast Atlantic (OSPAR areas))	OSPAR	IGO	conservation	Criteria for the Identification of Species and Habitats in need of Protection and their Method of Application (The Texel-Faial Criteria) (OSPAR Agreement 2019-03)
Regional Level (Northeast Atlantic and North Sea)	OSPAR	IGO	conservation	Biodiversity common indicators

ANNEX II. List of socio-economic and governance criteria

	CRITERIA	Criteria description/orientation
BLUE ECONOMY	Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to non-traditional activities	The area is (or can be) an important source of income and industrial jobs at industrial scale. < activities
	Area is important for fishery activity	The area is important for fishing, which occurs in that place or has the potential for it to occur. The area could also be important to the sector because it presents characteristics and conditions that sustain the fishery in another area. Eg: because it is a breeding and spawning zone.
	Area is important for shipping	It is a place of great interest for the navigation, for example, because the area has relevant characteristics that facilitate or support it (sufficient depth, legal reserves...), or in an indirect way because the area can support and regulate pressures like noise, discharges, etc.
	Area is important for dredging.	It is a place of interest (current or future) for activities related to dredging, both the extraction of sand (to increase the depth, for example) or the deposition of this dredged material.
	Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	The area has relevant characteristics that facilitate or support specific activities related to the blue economy (Aquaculture, offshore wind farm, biotechnology, tourism, ...)
	Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflict among users.	It is an area in which there are several current or potential uses and economic activities among which there may be conflicts of use for the same space or resources.
CULTURE	Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.	The area has a high value with respect to intangible cultural heritage, due to the existence of traditional activities or a culture that gives an ethnological value to the area.
	Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural. (monuments, etc)	The area is of relevance for its tangible cultural heritage. There are relevant historical or archaeological sites, as well as coastal and marine constructions or notable monuments for the local culture.

	Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.	It is an area with iconic coastal or marine species (seals, whales, an emblematic shorebird, etc.), or habitats highlighted by the local population (for example, a natural monument).
	Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.	It is a place where its landscape or aesthetic attractions stand out, or where the values associated with the area are culturally relevant (includes land-sea landscape, sea-land and submerged landscapes)
HUMAN WELLBEING	The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.	The use of living coastal and marine resources and their relationship with environmental quality is of particular importance regarding social, cultural, or local economic issues like fishing, recreation, tourism, and people's way of life and subsistence.
	Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.	Areas that preserve ancestral ways of life (in the use of resources, the activities they carry out, etc.), or settlements that are a sample of ancient cultures that inhabited the area.
	Area is important for locally-caught seafood	The specific activity of shellfishing occurs in that place or has great potential for it to take place there.
	Area important for recreation and leisure.	The area is important for developing activities related to maritime and/or coastal associated with free time, such as sailing, diving, etc.
	Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.	The area is important due to the presence of activities (usually traditional or low intensity), such as fishing production or shellfishing, it is essential for the community to have a safe flow of food supply for own consumption and access to quality food
	Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.	The marine area is a space to access another relevant area. For example, a maritime space that gives access to a fishing ground.
	Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	It is an important area for the well-being of the population that has an impact on their own health (mental health, physical health, etc...), either for the enjoyment of the area or its natural resources.

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EDUCATION AND SCIENCE	Area is important for educational interest	It is an area in which environmental education activities are developed or can be developed, due to its natural characteristics.
	Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes	The area has outstanding natural and/or socio-economic characteristics to be used as pilot area for restoration actions, sustainable development of different activities, compensation mechanisms, green infrastructures, nature-based solutions, etc. And/or the area has a scientific interest.
	An area that has high scientific interest.	Area considered of interest to the scientific community, because research is carried out or can be carried out.

	GOVERNANCE CRITERIA	CRITERIA description/orientation
STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT	Ecosystem based management approach	Ecosystem services are identified, assessed and incorporated to the management of the area
	Long term strategic adaptive management	Long term strategic management is adopted allowing a proactive, iterative and adaptive management. Lessons learned acquired along the different management cycles are being incorporated to management.
	Coherence management of the area	There is coherent coordination of international and sectoral policies and instruments in the area, and also of coastal-marine instruments to manage land-sea interactions. This coordination is articulated through inter-administrative and intra-administrative coordination mechanisms.
	Stakeholder participation	There is transparency and documents and information are shared with the interested parties, who participate in the management of the area and are satisfied with the participation process. The results of the participation are being incorporated into the management instruments. Public participation occurs in all management stages from the definition of objectives and the design of instruments to their implementation and evaluation.

	Equity	Clear objectives and social and cultural considerations are defined, adopted, and included in concrete measures. The measures adopted reduce conflicts between users and guarantee an equitable distribution of access to resources and areas, as well as the benefits that are generated.
PLANNING	Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies	The objectives established for the area are developed through instruments (strategies, plans, measures,...), and those have an associated person in charge of their correct implementation.
	Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy	The plan sets out clear economic objectives related to the principles of a sustainable blue economy
	Sustainable fishing management	Sustainable fishing management is carried out: catches are below biological safety limits, sustainable reproduction is guaranteed, sizes and imposed closures are respected, continuous monitoring is carried out and adaptive management is carried out based on the best available knowledge.
	Climate change measures established	Measures are established to face the uncertainty scenarios generated by climate change. Mitigation and adaptation measures are included.
	Cross-border cooperation	Mechanisms for cross-border cooperation exist and are used to ensure good planning, monitoring and implementation of transnational issues.
INFORMATION, KNOWLEDGE & EVALUATION	Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available	There are quality data and information accessible by the public and by the different administrations and sectors. All information and knowledge (including traditional knowledge) are considered in decision-making process in the area.
	Strategic Environmental Assessment	There is an environmental strategic assessment when developing policies or tools to manage the area
	Monitoring and evaluation	Monitoring and evaluation of the objectives and management measures of the area are being carried out

ANNEX III. Prioritization and ranking of the socio-economic criteria

Priority	Ranking	Socio-economic criteria	Examples (from previous criteria)
		Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to non-traditional activities	The area is (or can be) an important source of income and industrial jobs at industrial scale.< activities
		Area is important for fishery activity	The area is important for fishing, which occurs in that place or has the potential for it to occur. The area could also be important to the sector because it presents characteristics and conditions that sustain the fishery in another area. Eg: because it is a breeding and spawning zone.
		Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	The area has relevant characteristics that facilitate or support specific activities related to the blue economy (Aquaculture, offshore wind farm, biotechnology, tourism, ...)
		Area is important for shipping	It is a place of great interest for the navigation, for example, because the area has relevant characteristics that facilitate or support it (sufficient depth, legal reserves...), or in an indirect way because the area can support and regulate pressures like noise, discharges, etc.
		Area is important for dredging.	It is a place of interest (current or future) for activities related to dredging, both the extraction of sand (to increase the depth, for example) or the deposition of this dredged material.
		Area is important for locally-caught seafood	The specific activity of shell fishing occurs in that place or has great potential for it to take place there.
		Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.	It is a place where its landscape or aesthetic attractions stand out, or where the values associated with the area are culturally relevant (includes land-sea landscape, sea-land and submerged landscapes)
		The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.	The use of living coastal and marine resources and their relationship with environmental quality is of particular importance regarding social, cultural, or local economic issues like fishing, recreation,

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			tourism, and people's way of life and subsistence.
		Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.	Areas that preserve ancestral ways of life (in the use of resources, the activities they carry out, etc.), or settlements that are a sample of ancient cultures that inhabited the area.
		Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that suport local food security and sovereignty.	The area is important due to the presence of activities (usually traditional or low intensity), such as fishing production or shellfishing, it is essential for the community to have a safe flow of food supply for own consumption and access to quality food
		Area important for recreation and leisure.	The area is important for developing activities related to maritime and/or coastal associated with free time, such as sailing, diving, etc.
		Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.	The area has a high value with respect to intangible cultural heritage, due to the existence of traditional activities or a culture that gives an ethnological value to the area.
		Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural . (monuments, etc)	The area is of relevance for its tangible cultural heritage. There are relevant historical or archaeological sites, as well as coastal and marine constructions or notable monuments for the local culture.
		Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	It is an important area for the well-being of the population that has an impact on their own health (mental health, physical health, etc...), either for the enjoyment of the area or its natural resources.
		Area is important with occurency of iconic species/habitats for the local community.	It is an area with iconic coastal or marine species (seals, whales, an emblematic shorebird, etc.), or habitats highlighted by the local population (for example, a natural monument).

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		Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.	The marine area is a space to access another relevant area. For example, a maritime space that gives access to a fishing ground.
		Area is important to be managed due to spacial conflic among users.	It is an area in which there are several current or potential uses and economic activities among which there may be conflicts of use for the same space or resources.
		Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes	The area has outstanding natural and/or socio-economic characteristics to be used as pilot area for restoration actions, sustainable development of different activities, compensation mechanisms, green infrastructures, nature-based solutions, etc. And/or the area has a scientific interest.
		Area is important for educational interest	It is an area in which environmental education activities are developed or can be developed, due to its natural characteristics.
		An area that has high scientific interest.	Area considered of interest to the scientific community, because research is carried out or can be carried out.

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ANNEX IV. List of ecosystem services (Based on CICES 5.1. Marine Ecosystem Services)

Provisioning - biotic and abiotic (group and description)	
Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source
Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,
	The genetic information that is stored in wild animals that we can use
	Plants, fungi or algae that we can use for breeding
Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals
Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals
Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)
Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	The ways the physical environment contribute to human (e.g., wind energy, ozone, sunlight)
Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.
Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Water used as: drinking water, material and non-drinking (e.g., cooling) and energy (e.g., tidal)
Regulation & Maintenance - biotic and abiotic (group and description)	
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Pollination (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersal.
Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Reducing smells or screening unsightly things
Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Decomposing or filtering wastes
Pest and disease control	Controlling pests, invasive species and diseases

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Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Controlling or preventing soil loss, regulating the flows of water in our environment and protecting people from extreme events (that can protect people)
Regulation of soil quality	Ensuring the organic matter in our soils is maintained that maintains their characteristics necessary for human use
Water conditions	Controlling the chemical quality of saltwater enable human use and health.
Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulating our global climate and Regulating the physical quality of air for people
Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)
Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulating the physical quality of air for people (that affect people's well-being or comfort)
Cultural - biotic and abiotic (group and description)	
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature
	The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)
	The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from
Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem
Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved

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ANNEX V. Socio-economic criteria and associated ecosystem services for ranking exercise

Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities		Ranking	
The area is (or can be) an important source of income and industrial jobs at industrial scale.< activities			
Associated ecosystem services	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source	
	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.	
	Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,	
		The genetic information that is stored in wild animals that we can use	
		Plants, fungi or algae that we can use for breeding	
	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	
	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	
	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)	
	Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	The ways the physical environment contribute to human (e.g., wind energy, ozone, sunlight)	
	Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	
Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Water used as: drinking water, material and no-drinking (e.g., cooling) and energy (e.g., tidal)		

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	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Polinizacion (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersa.	
	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	

Blue: Provisioning services; Green: Regulation services; Purple: Cultural services

Area is important for fishery activity (e.g., priority stocks)		Ranking
Criterion	The area is important for fishing, which occurs in that place or has the potential for it to occur. The area could also be important to the sector because it presents characteristics and conditions that sustain the fishery in another area. Eg: because it is a breeding and spawning zone.	
Associated ecosystem services	Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,
		The genetic information that is stored in wild animals that we can use
		Plants, fungi or algae that we can use for breeding
	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Polinizacion (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersa.
	Pest and disease control	Controlling pests, invasive species and diseases

Blue: Provisioning services; Green: Regulation services; Purple: Cultural services

Area is important for the development of blue economy activities		Ranking
Criterion	The area has relevant characteristics that facilitate or support specific activities related to the blue economy (Aquaculture, offshore wind farm, biotechnology, tourism, ...)	
Asso	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source

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Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.	
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,	
	The genetic information that is stored in wild animals that we can use	
	Plants, fungi or algae that we can use for breeding	
Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	
Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	
Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)	
Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	The ways the physical environment contribute to human (e.g., wind energy, ozone, sunlight)	
Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	
Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Water used as: drinking water, material and no-drinking (e.g., cooling) and energy (e.g., tidal)	

Blue: Provisioning services; Green: Regulation services; Purple: Cultural services

Criterion	Area is important for shipping	Ranking
	It is a place of great interest for the navigation, for example, because the area has relevant characteristics that facilitate or support it (sufficient depth, legal reserves...), or in an indirect way because the area can support and regulate pressures like noise, discharges, etc.	

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Associated	Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)	
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Blue: Provisioning services; Green: Regulation services; Purple: Cultural services

Criterion	Area is important for dredging		Ranking
	It is a place of interest (current or future) for activities related to dredging, both the extraction of sand (to increase the depth, for example) or the deposition of this dredged material.		
Associated	Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)	

Blue: Provisioning services; Green: Regulation services; Purple: Cultural services

Criterion	Area is important for locally-caught seafood for public consumption		Ranking
	The specific activity of shell fishing occurs in that place or has great potential for it to take place there.		
Associated ecosystem services	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source	
	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food , materials or energy from wild plants.	
	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	
	Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	

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	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	

Blue: Provisioning services; Green: Regulation services; Purple: Cultural services

Criterion	Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.		Ranking
	It is a place where its landscape or aesthetic attractions stand out, or where the values associated with the area are culturally relevant (includes land-sea landscape, sea-land and submerged landscapes)		
Associated ES	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	
	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
	The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from		

Blue: Provisioning services; Green: Regulation services; Purple: Cultural services

Criterion	The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.		Ranking
	The use of living coastal and marine resources and their relationship with environmental quality is of particular importance regarding social,		

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cultural, or local economic issues like fishing, recreation, tourism, and people's way of life and subsistence.		
Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source	
Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.	
Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	
Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	
Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulating the physical quality of air for people (that affect people's well-being or comfort)	
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Polinización (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersa.	
Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Reducing smells or screening unsightly things	
Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Decomposing or filtering wastes	
Pest and disease control	Controlling pests, invasive species and diseases	
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Controlling or preventing soil loss, regulating the flows of water in our environment and protecting people from extreme events (that can protect people)	
Regulation of soil quality	Ensuring the organic matter in our soils is maintained that maintains their characteristics necessary for human use	
Water conditions	Controlling the chemical quality of salt water enable human use and health.	
	Researching and studying nature	

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	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	
	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	
	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	

Criterion	Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture (or cultures), or human interaction with the environment (specially in risk)		Ranking
	Areas that preserve ancestral ways of life (in the use of resources, the activities they carry out, etc.), or settlements that are a sample of ancient cultures that inhabited the area.		
	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can be used as a material, or energy source	
	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food , materials or energy from wild plants.	
	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	
	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	
	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)	
	Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	
		Researching and studying nature	

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	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	
	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	

Criterion	Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture (or cultures), or human interaction with the environment (specially in risk)		Ranking
	Areas that preserve ancestral ways of life (in the use of resources, the activities they carry out, etc.), or settlements that are a sample of ancient cultures that inhabited the area.		
	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can be used as a material, or energy source	
	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food , materials or energy from wild plants.	
	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	
	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	
	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)	
	Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	

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		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	
	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	

Criterion	Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.		Ranking	
	The area is important due to the presence of activities (usually traditional or low intensity), such as fishing production or shell fishing, it is essential for the community to have a safe flow of food supply for own consumption and access to quality food			
	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source		
	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.		
	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals		
	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals		
	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)		
	Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.		
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature		
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)		
The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from				

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	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem	
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Criterio	Important area for recreation and leisure.		Ranking	
	The area is important for developing activities related to maritime and/or coastal associated with free time, such as sailing, diving, etc.			
Associated ES	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health		
		Researching and studying nature		
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
			The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	

Criterion	Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.		Ranking	
	The area has a high value with respect to intangible cultural heritage, due to the existence of traditional activities or a culture that gives an ethnological value to the area.			
Associated ES	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem		
	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved		
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)		Researching and studying nature	
			The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	

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		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from
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Criterion	Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural . (monuments, etc)	Ranking	
			The area is of relevance for its tangible cultural heritage. There are relevant historical or archaeological sites, as well as coastal and marine constructions or notable monuments for the local culture.
Associated ES	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem	
	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
	The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from		

Criterion	Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	Ranking	
			It is an important area for the well-being of the population that has an impact on their own health (mental health, physical health, etc...), either for the enjoyment of the area or its natural resources.
Associated ES	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	
	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem	

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	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	

Criterion	Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.		Ranking
		It is an area with iconic coastal or marine species (seals, whales, an emblematic shorebird, etc.), or habitats highlighted by the local population (for example, a natural monument).	
Associated ES	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Polinizacion (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersa.	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	
	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	
	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem	
	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	

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Criterion	Area is important because allows the access to important areas for the marine users.		Ranking
	The marine area is a space to access another relevant area. For example, a maritime space that gives access to a fishing ground.		
Associated	Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)	

Criterion	Area is important to be manage due to spatial conflicts among users.		Ranking
	It is an area in which there are several current or potential uses and economic activities among which there may be conflicts of use for the same space or resources.		
Associated ES	Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)	
	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	

Criterion	Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and solution (restauration, sustainable development of different activities, compensation, green infrastructure/nature based solutions)		Ranking
	The area has outstanding natural and/or socio-economic characteristics to be used as pilot area for restoration actions, sustainable development of different activities, compensation mechanisms, green infrastructures, nature-based solutions, etc. And/or the area has a scientific interest.		
Asso	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source	

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Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.	
Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	
Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	
Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)	
Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	The ways the physical environment contribute to human (e.g., wind energy, ozone, sunlight)	
Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	
Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Water used as: drinking water, material and no-drinking (e.g., cooling) and energy (e.g., tidal)	
Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulating the physical quality of air for people (that affect people's well-being or comfort)	
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Polinizacion (coastal area), 'Gamete' disperse.	
Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Decomposing or filtering wastes	
Pest and disease control	Controlling pests, invasive species and diseases	
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Controlling or preventing soil loss, regulating the flows of water in our environment and protecting people from extreme events (that can protect people)	

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	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulating our global climate and Regulating the physical quality of air for people	
	Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	
	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	

Ranking	Area is important for educational interest		
	Ranking		
Ranking	It is an area in which environmental education activities are developed or can be developed, due to its natural characteristics.		
Associated ES	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	
		Researching and studying nature	

Ranking	An area that has high scientific interest.	
	Ranking	
Ranking	Area considered of interest to the scientific community, because research is carried out or can be carried out.	

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Associated ES	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	
	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	
		The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	
		The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	

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Sector	Activities	Pressures	Provisioning							Regulation & Maintenance										Cultural				Sum					
			Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Rearred aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Lifecycle maintenance, habitats and gene pool protection	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances	Pest and disease control	Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Regulation of soil quality	Water conditions	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (biotic: e.g., aves, natural; whales)	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value						
Tourism	Diving	Physical damage	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-2
Tourism	Diving	Biological disturbance	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
Tourism	Sailing vessels	Physical damage	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-4
Tourism	Sailing vessels	Biological disturbance	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Physical damage	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-4
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Other physical disturbance	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Biological disturbance	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-2
Tourism	Sport fishing	Physical damage	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-3
Tourism	Sport fishing	Other physical disturbance	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
Tourism	Sport fishing	Biological disturbance	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-3
Tourism	Cruise	Physical damage	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	-4
Tourism	Cruise	Other physical disturbance	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-6
Tourism	Cruise	Biological disturbance	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	-4
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-8
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-9
Tourism	Whale-watching	Other physical disturbance	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-3
Tourism	Whale-watching	Biological disturbance	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-11
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	0	-1	-1	0	-1	0	0	-1	0	-1	-1	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-9
Renewables	Wind farms	Other physical disturbance	0	0	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-3
Renewables	Wind farms	Biological disturbance	0	-1	-1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical loss	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-6
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical damage	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-5
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Other physical disturbance	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Biological disturbance	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical loss	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-7
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical damage	0	-1	-1	-1	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-5
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Other physical disturbance	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Biological disturbance	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	1	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-12
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	1	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-9
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-8
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-12
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systemic and/or intentional release of substances	-1	-1	-1	1	-1	-1	0	-1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-13
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	1	1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-12
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Biological disturbance	1	-1	-1	1	-1	0	0	-1	0	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-3
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Physical damage	0	-1	-1	0	1	-1	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	-1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	-5

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ANNEX III – Maritime activities pressures on the marine environment and their potential ecosystem service impacted.

For a better visualization, the excel table is accessed here: [Supporting material](#).

Sector	Activities	Pressures	ES Group	ES Section
Tourism	Diving	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Diving	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Diving	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sailing vessels	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Sailing vessels	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Tourism	Sailing vessels	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sailing vessels	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sailing vessels	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Tourism	Yatch and motorboats/motor vessels	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Sport fishing	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Physical damage	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Sport fishing	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Sport fishing	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Sport fishing	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Biological disturbance	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Sport fishing	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Physical damage	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Tourism	Cruise	Other physical disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Other physical disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Other physical disturbance	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Biological disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning

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Tourism	Cruise	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Biological disturbance	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Cruise	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Whale-watching	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Whale-watching	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Whale-watching	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Whale-watching	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Whale-watching	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Whale-watching	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Whale-watching	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Tourism	Whale-watching	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Tourism	Whale-watching	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical loss	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning

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Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Physical damage	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Wind farms	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Renewables	Wind farms	Biological disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical loss	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical loss	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical loss	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical loss	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical loss	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical loss	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical damage	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Physical damage	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Interference with hydrological processes	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Tidal	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical loss	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical loss	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical loss	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical loss	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical loss	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical loss	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical loss	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical damage	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Physical damage	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Interference with hydrological processes	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Renewables	Ocean energy - Wave	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance

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Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical loss	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Physical damage	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Other physical disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning

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Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Interference with hydrological processes	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Contamination by hazardous substances	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning

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Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Biological disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture in coastal or intertidal zones	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Physical damage	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Physical damage	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Physical damage	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance

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Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Other physical disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Interference with hydrological processes	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Interference with hydrological processes	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Interference with hydrological processes	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Interference with hydrological processes	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance

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Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Systematic and/or intentional release of substances	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Nutrient and organic matter enrichment	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Biological disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance

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Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Biological disturbance	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Aquaculture	Aquaculture at sea (hatcheries, floating cages and rafts)	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Physical damage	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Other physical disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Other physical disturbance	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Other physical disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Contamination by hazardous substances	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trawling	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning

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Fisheries	Gillnetting	Physical damage	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Physical damage	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Other physical disturbance	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Gillnetting	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Physical damage	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Other physical disturbance	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance

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Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Fisheries	Purse seine (with FADs or not)	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Longline	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Longline	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Longline	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Longline	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Longline	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Longline	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Longline	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Contamination by hazardous substances		Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Longline	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Longline	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Longline	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Longline	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Longline	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Other physical disturbance	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Other physical disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Other physical disturbance	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural

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Fisheries	Pots and traps	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Pots and traps	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Trammel net	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trammel net	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trammel net	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trammel net	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trammel net	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trammel net	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trammel net	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trammel net	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Trammel net	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Trammel net	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trammel net	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Trammel net	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	Cultural
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Other physical disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural

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Fisheries	Driftnetting	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Driftnetting	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Physical damage	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Other physical disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Other physical disturbance	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves, natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Other physical disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Contamination by hazardous substances	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance

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Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Dredges	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Other physical disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Biological disturbance	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Biological disturbance	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Biological disturbance	Pest and disease control	Regulation & Maintenance
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Biological disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Biological disturbance	Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g., caves. natural: whales)	Cultural
Fisheries	Push and stow net	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical loss	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical loss	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical loss	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical loss	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical loss	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical loss	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical loss	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical damage	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical damage	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical damage	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance

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Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Physical damage	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Biological disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Biological disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Biological disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Biological disturbance	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Deep-sea mining	Biological disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural

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Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical loss	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Regulation of soil quality	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Physical damage	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Other physical disturbance	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Other physical disturbance	Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Other physical disturbance	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Other physical disturbance	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Other physical disturbance	Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Cultural
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Other physical disturbance	Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	Cultural
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Contamination by hazardous substances	Genetic material (from plants, algae or fungi, animals and other organisms)	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Contamination by hazardous substances	Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Provisioning
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Contamination by hazardous substances	Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Contamination by hazardous substances	Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Contamination by hazardous substances	Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Contamination by hazardous substances	Water conditions	Regulation & Maintenance
Non-living marine resources extraction	Dredging	Contamination by hazardous substances	Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulation & Maintenance

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ANNEX VI – RESULTS PER TEST SITE

CADIZ BAY TEST SITE

Annex Table 1: Summary of case site: Bay of Cadiz

CASE SITE: CADIZ BAY (ZEC Fondos Marinos de Bahía de Cádiz (ES6120009))	
	<p>Location: South West of Spain (Gulf of Cadiz planning área)</p> <p>Name of MPA: ZEC Fondos Marinos de Bahía de Cádiz (ES6120009)</p> <p>Type of MPA: The priority in this MPA is to ensure a sustainable use of natural resources, so it is under VI category of UICN MPA</p> <p>MPA Plan: Yes, but remains only in the paper, not being implemented</p>
<p>About the process of CoP interaction to execute 4.1</p>	<p>The process was carried out in person with the CoP members. Some of them visited our office (we provided three different dates). Other stakeholders faced scheduling challenges, so we conducted the questionnaire at their locations. All interactions were conducted in person, as we anticipated potential questions. While some stakeholders were grouped together for the exercise at the same location and time, each individual completed it independently. From 17 members, a total of nine CoP members participated in Task 4.1, consisting of four government representatives, two MPA managers, two individuals from the private sector, and one from an NGO.</p>

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Adjustments made to adapt the exercise to the test site	Before interviewing all the CoP members, it was decided to test the exercise with two of them. This was important because it allowed us to enhance the exercise by combining the prioritization and ranking tasks, saving time and simplifying the process.
Main challenges faced in completing the exercise	The exercise proved to be somewhat time-consuming, primarily because it involved socio-economic criteria and their correlation with ecosystem services. Some of the stakeholders were unfamiliar with this approach, necessitating additional explanations. The case study featured a sizable CoP with 17 members (nine CoP members participated in this task), making it impractical to interview everyone due to scheduling constraints.
Main ecosystems	This MPA is valuable due to its seafloor covered in seagrasses. Among the various species present, the three distinct species of marine phanerogams are of outmost importance, as they constitute a vital habitat for fish breeding and rearing. These fish, in turn, rely on the surrounding fauna that thrives within these aquatic grasslands, thereby attracting a diverse range of aquatic birds.
Objectives of the MPA	The objective of the plan is to comply with current Spanish and European legislation in relation to the conservation of habitats and ecosystems of interest. To do this, the plan carries out an analysis of the area and establishes conservation priorities. Each of these priorities has its own objectives.
Main socio-economic characteristics of the MPA	The area around the Bay of Cádiz combines a wide range of interconnected uses and industries. Notably, it includes busy port operations in Cádiz, extensive industrial facilities in Puerto Real, and a growing tourism sector. This creates a zone of high activity, which surrounds another of exceptional ecological value, leading to various conflicts. The most prominent activities within the MPA encompass industrial port operations, navigation, tourism, and fishing. Additionally, activities like shellfish harvesting and aquaculture are also being developed in nearby areas.

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Governance criteria analysis

Annex Figure 1: Average of governance criteria prioritization of Bay of Cadiz. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 2: Average of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation - Bay of Cadiz Test Site.

Code	Criterion	Cadiz Bay	SD
CG_9	Climate change measures established	4,0	0,0
CG_1	Ecosystem based management approach	3,9	0,4
CG_6	Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies	3,9	0,4
CG_8	Sustainable fishing management	3,8	0,5
CG_2	Long term strategic adaptive management	3,6	0,5
CG_3	Coherence management of the area	3,6	0,5
CG_7	Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy	3,6	0,5
CG_11	Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available	3,6	0,5
CG_4	Stakeholder participation	3,5	0,5
CG_13	Monitoring and evaluation	3,5	0,5
CG_5	Equity	3,4	0,5
CG_12	Strategic Environmental Assessment	3,4	0,5
CG_10	Cross-border cooperation	2,0	1,9

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As can be seen in Annex Figure 1 and Annex Table 1, the CoP members of Cadiz Bay case study have scored the Governance criteria from 2 to 4. All the governance criteria are considered as “priority” or “high priority” in the MPA evaluated, unless the CG10 “Cross-border cooperation”. The Standard deviation in the responses is 0.5 or less to all criteria except CG10. The higher ranked criteria in the Cadiz Bay MPA are:

CG_9. Climate change measures established

CG_1. Ecosystem based management approach

CG_6. Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies

CG_8. Sustainable fishing management

On the contrary, criterion 10 “Cross-border cooperation“ has been scored with the lowest priority

Annex Table 3: Governance criteria ranking, average priority and frequency of answer for rank. - Bay of Cadiz Test Site.

Code	Criterion	Average Priority	Most Comm on Rank	Frequency
CG_1	Ecosystem based management approach	3,9	1	63%
CG_2	Long term strategic adaptive management	3,6	1	25%
CG_3	Coherence management of the area	3,6	1	38%
CG_4	Stakeholder participation	3,5	2	25%
CG_5	Equity	3,4	2	25%
CG_6	Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies	3,9	2	38%
CG_11		3,6	2	38%
CG_7	Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy	3,6	3	38%
CG_8	Sustainable fishing management	3,8	3	25%
CG_9	Climate change measures established	4,0	3	25%
CG_12	Strategic Environmental Assessment	3,4	3	25%
CG_13	Monitoring and evaluation	3,5	3	25%
CG_10	Cross-border cooperation	2,0	NAN	0%

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Asked about ranking the Governance criteria according to its importance to their MPA, a 63% of the respondents pointed out **CG1 Ecosystem based management approach** as the most important along with **CG3 Coherence management of the area** (38%) and **CG2 Long term strategic adaptive management** (25%).

Socio-economic criteria analysis

Annex Figure 2: Average of socio-economic criteria prioritization of Bay of Cadiz. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 4: Average of socio-economic criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - Bay of Cadiz Test Site.

Code	Criterion	Average Prio	SD
CSE_6	Area is important for locally-caught seafood	3,8	0,5
CSE_5	Area is important for dredging.	3,5	0,5
CSE_7	Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.	3,4	0,7
CSE_11	Area important for recreation and leisure.	3,4	0,7
CSE_12	Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.	3,4	0,7
CSE_18	Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes	3,3	0,7
CSE_19	Area is important for educational interest	3,3	0,7

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CSE_3	Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	3,1	1,1
CSE_10	Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.	3,1	1,0
CSE_20	An area that has high scientific interest.	3,1	0,6
CSE_16	Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.	2,9	1,6
CSE_17	Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.	2,9	1,1
CSE_14	Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	2,8	1,5
CSE_1	Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities	2,3	1,5
CSE_8	The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.	2,3	1,3
CSE_4	Area is important for shipping	2,1	2,0
CSE_9	Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.	2,1	1,6
CSE_13	Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc)	2,1	1,4
CSE_2	Area is important for fishery activity	2,0	1,5
CSE_15	Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.	2,0	1,5

The Cop members of the Cadiz Bay test site have given priority to many of the proposed socio-economic criteria, although most of them were scored with a standard deviation higher than 0.5. There are seven criteria with higher punctuation:

CSE_6 Area is important for locally-caught seafood

CSE_5 Area is important for dredging.

CSE_7 Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.

CSE_11 Area important for recreation and leisure.

CSE_12 Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value

CSE_18 Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes

CSE_19 Area is important for educational interest

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On the other hand, the socio-economic **criterion 2** “Area is important for fishery activity” **and 15** “Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community”, were scored with the lowest priority in this case study.

Annex Table 5: Socio-Economic criteria ranking, average priority, and frequency of answers for rank - Bay of Cadiz Test Site.

Code	Criterion	Average priority	Most common rank	Frequency
CSE_3	Area is important for the development of blue economy activities	3,1	1	66,7%
CSE_5	Area is important for dredging.	3,5	1	66,7%
CSE_6	Area is important for locally caught seafood	3,8	1	66,7%
CSE_7	Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.	3,4	1	50,0%
CSE_14	Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)	2,8	1	50,0%
CSE_16	Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.	2,9	1	50,0%
CSE_1	Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities	2,3	2	66,7%
CSE_4	Area is important for shipping	2,1	2	40,0%
CSE_9	Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.	2,1	2	66,7%
CSE_11	Area important for recreation and leisure.	3,4	2	75,0%
CSE_12	Area is important because of the presence of cultural symbolic value.	3,4	2	80,0%
CSE_15	Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.	2,0	2	50,0%
CSE_19	Area is important for educational interest	3,3	2	50,0%
CSE_20	An area that has high scientific interest.	3,1	2	66,7%

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CSE_10	Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.	3,1	3	66,7%
CSE_13	Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc)	2,1	3	66,7%
CSE_17	Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.	2,9	3	50,0%
CSE_2	Area is important for fishery activity	2,0	NAN	NAN
CSE_8	The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.	2,3	NAN	NAN
CSE_18	Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes	3,3	NAN	NAN

Asked about ranking the socio-economic criteria (Annex Table 5), the Cop members of the Cadiz Bay have ranked with a frequency ranging from 50 to 66,7%, as the six more important criteria are the followings:

CSE_3. Area is important for the development of blue economy activities

CSE_5. Area is important for dredging

CSE_6. Area is important for locally caught seafood

CSE_7. Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.

CSE_14. Area is important for health of coastal residents and/or resource users (mental health, physical health, etc)

CSE_16. Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users.

3.2.1.3. Ecosystem services analysis

Annex Table 6: Ecosystem services analysis: rank average and percentage of answers from the total possible - Bay of Cadiz

Ecosystem Services	Example	Ranking average	Percentage of answers from the total possible

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Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,	2,53	48%
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	Controlling or preventing soil loss, regulating the flows of water in our environment and protecting people from extreme events (that can protect people)	1,50	38%
Pest and disease control	Controlling pests, invasive species and diseases	2,97	42%
Water conditions	Controlling the chemical quality of salt water enable human use and health.	1,33	38%
Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	Decomposing or filtering wastes	2,33	31%
Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	Description: Plants that are cultivated in fresh or salt water that we eat, can use as a material, or energy source	2,32	41%
Regulation of soil quality	Ensuring the organic matter in our soils is maintained that maintains their characteristics necessary for human use	2,00	13%
Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	2,68	44%
Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	2,38	48%

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Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.	2,60	48%
Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	If needed, describe it.	3,25	19%
Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)	1,80	45%
Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	Natural inorganic materials from nature that we can use (e.g. salt)	2,88	38%
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Plants. fungi or algae that we can use for breeding	3,49	38%
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Politization (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersal.	1,65	68%
Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	Reducing smells or screening unsightly things	3,00	25%
Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulating our global climate and Regulating the physical quality of air for people	3,00	38%
Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulating the physical quality of air for people (that affect people well-being or comfort)	2,38	50%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	2,45	60%

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Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	2,53	41%
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	The genetic information that is stored in wild animals that we can use	3,11	38%
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem	3,05	48%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	2,61	46%
Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	2,77	50%
Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	The ways the physical environment contribute to human (e.g., wind energy, ozone, sunlight)	2,85	42%
Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g. caves; Natural e.g. whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	2,60	65%
Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	Water used as: drinking water, material and no-drinking (e.g., cooling) and energy (e.g., tidal)	1,89	33%

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Annex Figure 3: Bay of Cadiz - Left Image: Ecosystem services ranking average. Right image: Ecosystem services ranking average from frequency higher than 50%.

The CoP members of Bay of Cádiz case study have ranked the ecosystem services from 1,33 to 3,49, being the first five ES ranked in Annex Figure 3 as the most important to their MPAs, ranging from 1,33 to 1,89. These ES are the followings:

- Controlling the chemical quality of salt water enable human use and health.
- Controlling or preventing soil loss, regulating the flows of water in our environment and protecting people from extreme events (that can protect people)
- Water used as: drinking water, material and no-drinking (e.g., cooling) and energy (e.g., tidal)
- Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Politization (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersal.
- Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes

Moreover, there are four ES that have an average percentage of answers from the total possible higher than 50%. These ES are:

- Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Politization (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersal.
- Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health
- The things in nature that we think should be conserved
- Researching and studying nature

The CoP members of the Bay of Cádiz have given importance to cultural and regulation Ecosystem Services.

The results obtained regarding the relationship between ecosystem services and socio-economic criteria can be collectively reviewed for all case studies in section 3.3 (all sea basins) of the results.

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NORTH SEA CASE SITE

Annex Table 7: Summary of case site: North Sea

NORTH SEA	
	<p>Location: Belgium part of the North Sea</p> <p>Name of MPA: Vlaamse Banken Special Area of Conservation</p> <p>Type of MPA: Protected area with sustainable use of natural resources</p> <p>MPA Plan: Yes, but most management measures are currently not yet being enforced</p>
<p>About the process of CoP interaction to execute 4.1</p>	<p>Google Jamboard, MS Excel were the tools used to perform the exercise. It was carried out by sending the Google Jamboard link and the link to the Excel sheet to the CoP members via email, and in the Google Jamboard/Excel link, and email instructions were given for the exercise. Five CoP members filled out the exercise: two responses from the governing authority; One from an industry representative; one from the fisheries institute (was carried out by two people together); one from an environmental NGO. Four CoP members carried out the exercise independently, one member (env. NGO) carried out the exercise in person at VLIZ together with an MSP4BIO project partner.</p>
<p>Adjustments made to adapt the exercise to the test site</p>	<p>The main adjustment made was that the decision was made to focus on an existing MPA (Vlaamse Banken) so we did not ask CoP members to fill in the exercise for a proposed MPA.</p>

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	We also designed the exercise so it could be completed individually as we did not have time to schedule meetings with the CoP members.
Main challenges faced in completing the exercise	CoP members understand it's necessary to consider the socio-economic context, but they don't see these criteria as something to define priorities with, rather issues that needed to be taken into account when developing policy. Some governance criteria were felt to be quite similar to each other or have a lack of nuance. There was confusion about whether it's about the current practice or about their perception (we clarified it's about their perception)
Main ecosystems	Sand banks, gravel beds and sand mason worm aggregations
Objectives of the MPA	<p>Vlaamse Banken: Habitat type 1110 (shallow sandbanks)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Conservation of the spatial coverage of sand banks 2. Functional characteristics of shallow sandbanks as spawning and nursery grounds should be conserved 3. Non-native species introduced by human activities should not change the ecosystem 4. Increase in abundance of fragile species 5. The benthic ecosystem should provide enough food for higher trophic levels 6. Ecological quality of benthic habitats from the <i>Abra alba</i> biotope should remain <p>Vlaamse Banken: Habitat type 1170 (<i>L. conchilega</i> aggregations)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. The spontaneous development of <i>Lanice conchilega</i> aggregations should not be hindered <p>Vlaamse Banken: Habitat type 1170 (reefs/gravel beds)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. There is at least a conservation of the areal coverage of naturally occurring hard substrates 9. There is recovery of natural benthic ecosystems in the gravel beds <p>Marine mammals</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 10. The spatial coverage of native marine mammals is stable and not smaller than the reference area

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	<ol style="list-style-type: none">11. The quality of the habitat in terms of food supply, contaminants, underwater noise and marine litter is suitable for the support of different phases of the life cycle of marine mammals12. The incidental mortality of marine mammals caused by humans is lower than the level at which the species would be endangered, to guarantee the survival of the species13. Injury of marine mammals due to human interaction is avoided14. There is an increase in places that are being used by seals as a resting place, and a decrease in the disturbance of those resting places <p>Seabirds</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">15. There is no decrease in the spatial coverage of the seabird habitats16. The population of protected seabirds is conserved17. The quality of the habitat in terms of food supply, contaminants, marine litter is suitable for supporting the different phases of the life cycle of seabirds18. Disturbance of seabirds is avoided19. The available habitat and the migration potential of birds is conserved20. Injury and death of seabirds caused by human activities should be avoided
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<p>Main socio-economic characteristics of the MPA</p>	<p>Existing use within the Vlaamse Banken MPA includes sand and gravel extraction, dredging and dumping of dredged materials, as well as shipping, aquaculture and defence. For future use, two zones that are designated for offshore wind energy generation overlap with the MPA, which may also be used for passive fishing in the future.</p> <p>Overview of activities that take place within the Vlaamse Banken MPA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Shipping: Anchorage place; Shipping route; Precautionary area; Area to be avoided.• Dredging and dumping: Dumping site for dredged materials; Dredging location.• Sand and gravel extraction: Monitoring zone; Sand extraction zone• Electricity: Proposed wind farm zones (which overlaps with a proposed passive fishing zone); Subsea cable link UK-Belgium• Aquaculture: Pilot projects aquaculture; Westdiep sea farm (mussels etc); Development area for aquaculture; Development area for commercial and industrial activities• Maritime heritage: Sites of underwater cultural heritage older than 100 years; (Protected) shipwrecks; Shrimp fishing on horseback.• Defense: Area for shooting exercises (on floating objects); Area for sweeping mines• Research: Measuring station; Reference area for calibrating measuring instruments
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Governance criteria analysis

Annex Figure 4: Average of governance criteria prioritization North Sea Test Site. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 8: Average value of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - North Sea Test.

Criterion	Prioritization	SD
CG_13	3,6	0,55
CG_1	3,4	0,89
CG_8	3,4	0,89
CG_6	3,2	1,10
CG_11	3,2	0,45
CG_2	3,0	1,00
CG_10	3,0	0,71
CG_3	2,8	0,84
CG_4	2,8	1,10
CG_12	2,8	0,84
CG_9	2,0	0,71
CG_7	1,8	2,05
CG_5	1,6	1,14

As showed in Annex Figure 4 and Annex Table 8, the CoP members of North Sea case study have scored the Governance criteria from 1,6 to 3,6. Seven governance criteria are considered of high priority, although most of them have standard deviations higher than 0,5. The most prioritized criteria in the North Sea are:

CG_13. Monitoring and evaluation

CG_1. Ecosystem based management approach

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CG_8. Sustainable fishing management

CG_6. Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies

CG_11. Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available

The lowest priority was given to criteria 5 “equity” and 7 “Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy”, although both have the highest scores in terms of deviation among the given responses.

Annex Table 9: Governance criteria ranking. average priority, and frequency of answers for rank – North Sea Test Site.

Criterion	Mean Priority	Most Common Rank	Frequency
CG_1	3,4	1	60%
CG_13	3,6	3	40%
CG_11	3,2	6	40%
CG_2	3	9	60%
CG_10	3	11	40%
CG_6	3,2	02 to 10	0%
CG_8	3,4	02 to11	0%

In the North Sea the governance criteria ranked as most important, with a frequency of 60% among the respondents, is the **CG_1** “Ecosystem based approach” (40% of frequency), the second is the **CG_13** “Monitoring and evaluation”, and the third is **CG_11** “Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available” (40% of frequency).

On the other hand, **CG_10** “Cross-border cooperation” was ranked as the least important (40% of frequency).

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Socio-economic criteria analysis

Annex Figure 5: Average of socio-economic criteria prioritization of North Sea. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 10: Average value of socio-economic criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - North Sea Test Site.

Criterion	Average Priority	SD
CSE_17	3,4	0,55
CSE_20	3,4	0,55
CSE_18	2,8	0,84
CSE_11	2,4	0,55
CSE_19	2,4	0,89
CSE_15	2	1,22
CSE_2	1,8	1,79
CSE_3	1,8	2,05
CSE_6	1,6	1,14
CSE_1	1,4	1,95
CSE_8	1,4	1,14
CSE_14	1,4	0,89
CSE_16	1,4	1,52
CSE_10	1,2	0,84
CSE_4	1	0,71
CSE_7	1	1,22
CSE_5	0,8	1,10
CSE_12	0,8	1,30

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CSE_9	0,6	0,89
CSE_13	0,6	1,34

Only two of the socio-economic criteria have been scored as “high priority” by the CoP members of the North Sea case study (See Annex Figure 5 and Annex Table 10). Both have the lowest (but still high) standard deviation with a 0,5. Many of the criteria have a standard deviation in the responses higher than 1. The two criteria of high priority are:

CSE_17. Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.

CSE_20. An area that has high scientific interest.

On the other hand, there are two criteria with the lowest prioritization score. These are:

CSE_9. Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.

CSE_13. Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural. (monuments, etc).

Annex Table 11: Socio-economic ranking, average priority, and frequency of answers for rank – North Sea Test Site.

CG	Average Priority	Most Common Rank	Frequency
CSE_3	1,8	1	0,4
CSE_20	3,4	2	0,4
CSE_17	3,4	3	0,4
CSE_2	1,8	4	0,4
CSE_18	2,8	4	0,4
CSE_19	2,4	6	0,4
CSE_6	1,6	8	0,4
CSE_14	1,4	9	0,4
CSE_15	2	11	0,4
CSE_10	1,2	13	0,4
CSE_4	1	15	0,4
CSE_9	0,6	17	0,6
CSE_12	0,8	19	0,4
CSE_13	0,6	20	0,4
CSE_1	1,4	NAN	NAN
CSE_5	0,8	NAN	NAN
CSE_7	1	NAN	NAN
CSE_8	1,4	NAN	NAN
CSE_11	2,4	NAN	NAN
CSE_16	1,4	NAN	NAN

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Asked about ranking the socio-economic criteria (Annex Table 11), the Cop members of the North Sea have ranked with a frequency ranging from 50 to 66,7%, as the six more important criteria are the followings:

CSE_3. Area is important for the development of blue economy activities

CSE_20. An area that has high scientific interest

CSE_17. Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users

CSE_2. Area is important for fishery activity

CSE_18. Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes

CSE_3. Area is important for the development of blue economy activities

Ecosystem services analysis

Annex Table 12: Ecosystem services analysis: rank average and percentage of answers from the total possible – North Sea Test Site.

Ecosystem Sevices		Ranking average	Percentage of answers from the total possible
Offshore renewable energy		1,17	40%
Navigation surface		1,20	60%
Nursery and habitat maintenance		2,10	36%
Coastal protection		2,25	40%
Aesthetic experience		2,32	42%
Cultural heritage		2,59	44%
Climate regulation		3,00	20%
Water quality regulation		3,00	20%
Wild aquatic animals		3,00	32%
Scientific research		3,01	43%
Recreation		3,26	40%
Farmed aquatic plants		3,70	27%
Farmed aquatic animals		4,10	36%
Sand and other minerals		4,38	30%

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Annex Figure 6: Figure 11. Ecosystem services ranking average- North Sea

In this case, Annex Figure 6 does not include the graph related to the ranking of ecosystem services with a response frequency greater than 50% due to the absence of high frequencies in the obtained responses.

The CoP members of North Sea case study have ranked the ecosystem services from 1.17 to 4.38, being the first five ES ranked in Annex Table 12 as the most important to their MPAs, with a rank between 1.17 and 2.32. These ES are the followings:

- Offshore renewable energy
- Navigation surface
- Nursery and habitat maintenance
- Coastal protection
- Aesthetic experience

In this case study, only one of the ecosystem services has been selected by more than 50% of the participants. It is the service "Navigation surface", with a value of 1.2 and accepted by 60% of the participants.

The results obtained regarding the relationship between ecosystem services and socio-economic criteria can be collectively reviewed for all case studies in section 3.3 (all sea basins) of the results.

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BALTIC SEA CASE SITE

Annex Table 13: Summary of case site: Baltic Sea

BALTIC SEA	
	<p>Location: Polish part of the Baltic Sea</p> <p>Name of MPA: Zalew Wislany i Mierzeja Wislana (Vistula Lagoon and Vistula Spit)</p> <p>Type of MPA: NATURA 2000 (SCI) (Also HELCOM MPA). IUCN VI category</p> <p>MPA Plan: On Polish side of the Lagoon two Natura 2000 areas (birds and habitats) are established, covering entirely the Lagoon and only plan for SCI is adopted.</p>
<p>About the process of CoP interaction to execute 4.1</p>	<p>Commencing the process, a presentation was delivered by the test site lead, offering an overview of Task 5.1 results. The presentation highlighted key issues related to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The current status of the MPA network. • The integration of social and economic aspects with MPAs. • The coherence between MPAs and the (transboundary) Marine Spatial Planning (MSP) process, along with related governance structures such as the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD). • The (re)building of stakeholder confidence in the MPA/MSP implementation. <p>Following the presentation, each socio-economic and governance criterion was explained in detail. CoP members were then instructed to rank these criteria for their current MPA network and their anticipated future MPAs separately. The ranking utilized the categories of "high priority," "priority," and "not priority". The MIRO Board platform was used to</p>

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	facilitate online interaction. This platform enabled the organized listing of both socio-economic and governance criteria.
Adjustments made to adapt the exercise to the test site	Each criterion for socio-economic and governance aspects was abbreviated and simplified to enhance comprehension for CoP members. The engagement process was conducted entirely online due to logistical constraints. There was one meeting held for this purpose. A total of seven CoP members representing three Baltic Sea countries participated in the exercise. These CoP members were drawn from their respective countries' MSP-MPA authorities and research institutes.
Main challenges faced in completing the exercise	The regional attributes of the Baltic Sea test site presented certain challenges. A limited number of CoP members were able to participate in the exercise to represent their respective countries. CoP members raised concerns regarding the perceived lack of objectivity in the rankings, emphasizing the need for more extensive and comprehensive ranking surveys. Furthermore, selecting criteria for a sizable MPA network proved to be a complex task. CoP members expressed the view that such an exercise might be more effectively conducted on a local scale. However, it was communicated to CoP members that a localized version of this exercise will be carried out in the Vistula Lagoon MPA within the Baltic Sea.
Main ecosystems	The Vistula Lagoon, shared by two countries Poland and Russia, is a shallow, brackish water area, important from the point of view of migratory and nesting water birds as well as the brackish and sea fish species, having their spawning there.
Objectives of the MPA	The objective of this plan is to establish a protection plan for the special area of conservation known as "Zalew Wiślany and Mierzeja Wiślana" (PLH280007), hereinafter referred to as the "Natura 2000 Area." This plan aims to outline various elements, including the description of the area's boundaries, identification of existing and potential threats to the conservation of natural habitats and species, determination of conditions for maintaining or restoring the appropriate state of protection for the objects of conservation, as well as the development of protective measures and monitoring mechanisms. The plan's implementation is intended to contribute to the preservation and integrity of the Natura 2000 Area until December 31, 2042, in accordance with environmental protection regulations.

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Main socio-economic characteristics of the MPA	The Vistula Lagoon MPA in the Baltic Sea is a hub of diverse socio-economic activities. These include land reclamation, watercourse modifications, coastal defense, seabed restructuring, non-renewable energy generation, fishing, transport, urban development, waste management, tourism, research, and education. Military operations are regulated under Article 2(2). This multifaceted environment presents both opportunities and challenges for conservation and sustainable development.
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Governance criteria analysis

Annex Figure 7: Average of governance criteria prioritization of Baltic Sea (Regional and MPA approach). Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 14: Average value of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - Baltic Sea (Regional and MPA approach).

Criterion	Baltic	SD
CG_1	3,7	0,6
CG_3	3,5	0,7
CG_12	3,5	0,7
CG_4	3,0	0,0
CG_6	3,0	nan
CG_7	3,0	nan
CG_8	2,3	2,1
CG_11	2,3	2,1
CG_10	1,5	2,1
CG_2	0,0	NaN
CG_5	0,0	nan
CG_9	0,0	0,0
CG_13	0,0	0,0

Criterion	Baltic MPA (Poland)
CG_3	4,0
CG_4	4,0
CG_6	4,0
CG_10	4,0
CG_5	4,0
CG_9	4,0
CG_12	3,5
CG_11	3,0
CG_13	3,0
CG_7	2,5
CG_8	1,5
CG_1	1,0
CG_2	nan

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As can be seen in Annex Figure 7 and Annex Table 14, the CoP members of the Baltic Sea case study have scored the Governance criteria from 0 to 4. In the Poland MPA it was from 1 to 4. 6 from the 13 governance criteria are considered as “priority” or “high priority”, 9 in the Polish MPA evaluated. The Standard deviation in the responses is higher to 0.5 in all cases, except CG_4, CG_9 and CG_13. The higher ranked criteria in the Baltic MPA are:

- CG_1.** Ecosystem based management approach
- CG_3.** Coherence management of the area
- CG_12.** Strategic Environmental Assessment
- CG_4.** Stakeholder participation
- CG_6.** Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies
- CG_7.** Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy

On the contrary, the following 7 criterion have been scored with the lowest priority, in this order:

- CG_8.** Sustainable fishing management
- CG_11.** Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available
- CG_10.** Cross-border cooperation
- CG_2.** Long term strategic adaptive management
- CG_5.** Equity
- CG_9.** Climate change measures established
- CG_13.** Monitoring and evaluation

In the case of the Poland MPA, the higher ranked criteria are:

- CG_3.** Coherence management of the area
- CG_4.** Stakeholder participation
- CG_6.** Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies
- CG_10.** Cross-border cooperation
- CG_5.** Equity
- CG_9.** Climate change measures established
- CG_12.** Strategic Environmental Assessment
- CG_11.** Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available
- CG_13.** Monitoring and evaluation

On the contrary, the following 4 criterion have been scored with the lowest priority, in this order:

- CG_7.** Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy
- CG_8.** Sustainable fishing management

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CG_1. Ecosystem based management approach

CG_2. Long term strategic adaptive management

No ranking exercise was performed in this test site.

Socio-economic criteria analysis

Annex Figure 8: Average of socio-economic criteria prioritization of Baltic Sea (Regional and MPA approach). Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 15: Table 27. Average value of socio-economic criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - Baltic Sea (Regional and MPA approach).

Criterion	Baltic	SD
CSE_3	4,0	NAN
CSE_9	4,0	0,0
CSE_2	3,7	0,6
CSE_4	3,5	0,7
CSE_20	3,5	0,7
CSE_6	3,3	0,6
CSE_11	3,0	NAN

Criterion	Baltic MPA
CSE_2	4,0
CSE_10	4,0
CSE_13	4,0
CSE_3	3,0
CSE_4	3,0
CSE_6	3,0
CSE_7	3,0

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CSE_1	2,3	2,1
CSE_13	2,0	1,7
CSE_12	0,0	NAN
CSE_16	0,0	NAN
CSE_17	0,0	NAN
CSE_18	0,0	NAN
CSE_5	NAN	NAN
CSE_7	NAN	NAN
CSE_8	NAN	NAN
CSE_10	NAN	NAN
CSE_14	NAN	NAN
CSE_15	NAN	NAN
CSE_19	NAN	NAN

CSE_14	3,0
CSE_17	3,0
CSE_5	2,0
CSE_8	2,0
CSE_11	2,0
CSE_12	2,0
CSE_16	2,0
CSE_19	2,0
CSE_20	2,0
CSE_15	1,0
CSE_18	1,0
CSE_1	0,0
CSE_9	NAN

The Cop members of the Baltic Sea test site have given priority to many of the proposed socio-economic criteria, although most of them were scored with a standard deviation higher than 0.5. There are seven criteria with higher punctuation, in this order:

- CSE_3.** Area is important for the development of blue economy activities
- CSE_9.** Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.
- CSE_2.** Area is important for fishery activity
- CSE_4.** Area is important for shipping
- CSE_20.** An area that has high scientific interest.
- CSE_11.** Area important for recreation and leisure.

In the case of Poland MPA, 9 criteria were selected with high or very high priority, highlighting the following:

- CSE_2.** Area is important for fishery activity
- CSE_10.** Area is important because of the presence of cultural and tradition activities that support local food security and sovereignty.
- CSE_13.** Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc)

On the other hand, the socio-economic criterion scored with the lowest priority in this case study were:

- CSE_1.** Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities

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CSE_18. Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes

CSE_15. Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.

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NORTH-WESTERN MEDITERRANEAN CASE SITE

Annex Table 16: Summary of case site: North-western Mediterranean

NORTH-WESTERN MEDITERRANEAN (Pelagos Sanctuary area and Gulf of Lion)	
	<p>Location: North Western of Mediterranean Sea Name of MPA: Pelagos Sanctuary for Mediterranean Marine Mammals Type of MPA: Specially Protected Area of Mediterranean Importance (SPAMI) under the Barcelona Convention MPA Plan: Yes</p>
<p>About the process of CoP interaction to execute 4.1</p>	<p>The engagement process was conducted entirely online. There was one meeting held between NW-Med test site leaders to prepare this interaction and decide on the area to work on. It was decided to work on the Pelagos area which is transboundary and allows to interact with French and Italian CoP members jointly. Several contacts via e-mails were made to engage CoP members and convince them to participate in the meeting. We finally organized 2 meetings to present the exercise to the CoP members who agreed to volunteer for the task:</p>

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - One meeting in French with the person leading the French Delegation of the Pelagos Sanctuary Agreement within Port-Cros National Park. The meeting was dedicated to the evaluation of ecosystem services. - One meeting with one Pelagos representative, WWF representatives and 2 Italian CoP members who are working on MSP and MPA related topics. At the beginning of the meeting, the general approach was presented to the CoP members who participated in the evaluation process. Then, the test site leaders explained thoroughly the guidelines to conduct the exercise as the CoP members were asked to carry it out individually after the workshops. 2 evaluations were finally received after the meeting.
<p>Adjustments made to adapt the exercise to the test site</p>	<p>First, we decided to only evaluate the offshore part of the Pelagos area as it would have been difficult to evaluate socio-economic criteria for coastal areas where uses are very distinct from one zone to another.</p> <p>Then, regarding the methodology of the evaluation, CoP members advised to better specify the sense of the word « important » in the definition of the socio-economic criteria. They decided to define it as « concerned / affected » (example: the area is concerned by fishery activity).</p>
<p>Main challenges faced in completing the exercise</p>	<p>It was difficult to assess/score some activities that may take place in very localized places (for instance dredging) as the Pelagos area is really vast.</p>
<p>Main ecosystems</p>	<p>The general ecological importance of the marine ecosystem in of this area has been confirmed in the 2010s by the UN Convention on Biodiversity, which identified two EBSAs (Ecologically or Biologically Important Marine Areas) fully overlapping the Pelagos Sanctuary: the North-western Mediterranean Pelagic Ecosystems and the North-western Mediterranean Benthic Ecosystems. More recently the IUCN identified two IMMAs (Important Marine Mammal Areas) in this region: the Western Ligurian Sea and Genoa Canyon IMMA (a key habitat for the Cuvier's beaked whale) and the North West Mediterranean Sea, Slope and Canyon System IMMA (important habitat for fin and sperm whales and extending further beyond Pelagos).</p> <p>The Sanctuary is one of the most productive pelagic environments in the Mediterranean Sea, but also one of those under the heaviest anthropic pressure.</p>

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<p>Objectives of the MPA</p>	<p>Harmonise and adopt appropriate conservation measures for marine mammals in accordance with those adopted within the framework of ACCOBAMS and the Barcelona Convention, to ensure a favourable conservation status of these species, by protecting their populations and habitats from the direct and indirect negative impacts of activities in a given geographical area.</p> <p>The new management plan puts in place a new governance by acting at several organisational levels. The Pelagos Agreement Management becomes a platform for co-design (with stakeholders) adaptive interventions, tools, policies and activities to promote the sustainable management of Pelagos as a critical ecosystem for marine mammals.</p> <p>Three priority thematics have been defined for this plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pelagos against pollution (including the EcoPorts) - Pelagos Slow Travel (including Sustainable boating) - Improved governance
<p>Main socio-economic characteristics of the MPA</p>	<p>The Pelagos area is really important for shipping as one third of Mediterranean traffic is located within Pelagos.</p> <p>The area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community as 8 marine mammals species are protected within the sanctuary.</p> <p>Then, the area is used to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and to scientific purposes. Pelagos works as a laboratory area for management practices. 60 studies have been funded through Pelagos in the last 20 years regarding marine mammals (for instance, a guide to study the nautical activities' impacts on marine mammals, a reflexion group for derogation for the approach of marine mammals 100m, REPCET tool test, underwater noise study). The area is used to test solutions which are then extended to the rest of the Mediterranean basin notably for the municipalities that have adhered to the charter of the sanctuary.</p>

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Governance criteria analysis

Annex Figure 9: Average of governance criteria prioritization of North-western Mediterranean. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 17: Average value of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD)- North-western Mediterranean

Criterion	Average Priority	SD
CG_1	4,0	0,0
CG_2	4,0	0,0
CG_4	4,0	0,0
CG_5	4,0	0,0
CG_7	4,0	0,0
CG_8	4,0	0,0
CG_9	4,0	0,0
CG_13	4,0	NAN
CG_3	3,5	0,7
CG_6	3,5	0,7
CG_10	3,5	0,7
CG_11	3,5	0,7
CG_12	3,5	0,7

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As can be seen in Annex Figure 9 and Annex Table 17, the CoP members of the Mediterranean case study have scored the Governance criteria from 3,5 to 4. All the governance criteria are considered as “priority” or “high priority” in the MPA evaluated. The standard deviation in the responses in 0.5 or less to all criteria except CG3, CG6, CG10, CG11 and CG12, with 0.5 of SD. The higher ranked criteria are:

- CG_1.** Ecosystem based management approach
- CG_2.** Long term strategic adaptive management
- CG_4.** Stakeholder participation
- CG_5.** Equity
- CG_7.** Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy
- CG_8.** Sustainable fishing management
- CG_9.** Climate change measures established
- CG_13.** Monitoring and evaluation

On the contrary, the following 5 criterion have been scored with 3.5:

- CG_3.** Coherence management of the area
- CG_6.** Instruments to ensure and guide development and implementation of marine policies
- CG_10.** Cross-border cooperation
- CG_11.** Decision making is based on best information and knowledge available
- CG_12.** Strategic Environmental Assessment

Annex Table 18: Average value of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - North-western Mediterranean

Criterion	Average Priority	Ranking variation
CG_1	4	1 to 2
CG_2	4	2 to 4
CG_4	4	NAN
CG_9	4	3 to 5
CG_8	4	6 to 8
CG_5	4	13
CG_7	4	12
CG_13	4	10
CG_3	3,5	8 to 9

Asked about ranking the socio-economic criteria (Annex Table 18), the Cop members of the North-western Mediterranean have ranked as the three more important criteria the followings:

- CSE_1.** Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities
- CSE_2.** Area is important for fishery activity

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CSE_9. Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.

On the contrary, criterion **5 “Area is important for dredging”** and **7 “Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value”** were ranked with the latest positions.

Socio-economic criteria analysis

Annex Figure 10: Average of socio-economic criteria prioritization of - North-western Mediterranean. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 19: Average value of socio-economic criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - North-western Mediterranean.

Criterion	Average Priority	SD
CSE_4	4,00	0,00
CSE_7	4,00	0,00
CSE_8	4,00	0,00
CSE_11	4,00	0,00
CSE_15	4,00	0,00
CSE_18	4,00	0,00
CSE_14	3,50	0,71
CSE_17	3,50	0,71
CSE_20	3,50	0,71
CSE_13	3,00	0,00
CSE_9	2,50	2,12
CSE_19	2,50	2,12

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CSE_3	2,00	1,41
CSE_12	2,00	1,41
CSE_1	1,50	0,71
CSE_5	1,50	2,12
CSE_10	1,50	0,71
CSE_16	1,50	0,71
CSE_2	1,00	1,41
CSE_6	1,00	1,41

The CoP members of the North-western Mediterranean have given the most priority (with no deviation among respondents) to the following socio-economic criteria:

CSE_4. Area is important for shipping

CSE_7. Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.

CSE_8. The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.

CSE_11. Area important for recreation and leisure

CSE_15 Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.

CSE_18 Area with current/potential importance to explore and demonstrate approaches and management solutions, and/or to scientific purposes

On the other hand, criteria 2 “Area is important for fishery activity” and 6 “Area is important for locally-caught seafood” were scored with the lowest priority in this case study.

Annex Table 20: Table 33. Socio-economic criteria ranking- North-western Mediterranean.

CG	Priority	Ranking	
CSE_4	4	2	3
CSE_11	4	7	4
CSE_15	4	1	2
CSE_18	4	3	1
CSE_7	4	8	
CSE_8	4	9	

Asked about ranking the socio-economic criteria (Annex Table 20), the CoP members of the North-western Mediterranean have ranked as the three most important criteria the followings:

CSE_15. Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.

CSE_13. Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc)

CSE_4. Area is important for shipping.

Ecosystem services analysis

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Annex Table 21: Table 34. Ecosystem services analysis: rank average and percentage of answers from the total possible - North-western Mediterranean

Ecosystem Services	ES	Ranking average	Percentage of answers from the total possible
Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from reared animals	1	33%
Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	If needed, describe it. (e.g. Spatial support to enable human uses)	1	58%
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	Providing habitats for wild plants and animals that can be useful to us (nursery), and Politization (coastal area), 'Gamete' dispersal.	1,25	67%
Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild animals	1,5	33%
Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	The things in nature that we think should be conserved	1,92	48%
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	Animals used for replenishing stock or for breeding,	2	33%
Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	Food, materials or energy from wild plants.	2	33%
Atmospheric composition and conditions	Regulating our global climate and Regulating the physical quality of air for people	2	67%
Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	Regulating the physical quality of air for people (that affect people well-being or comfort)	2	33%

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Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	Researching and studying nature	2,12	56%
Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g. caves; Natural e.g. whales)	Using the environment for sport, ecotourism, recreation, health	2,87	67%
Pest and disease control	Controlling pests, invasive species and diseases	3	33%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The beauty of nature (appreciated for their inherent beauty)	3,15	81%
Non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	The ways the physical environment contribute to human (e.g., wind energy, ozone, sunlight)	3,5	33%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	The things in nature that help people identify with the history or culture of where they live or come from	4,12	50%
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	The things in nature that have spiritual importance for people or is a local emblem	4,4	47%

Annex Figure 11: Figure 16. North-western Mediterranean - Left Image: Ecosystem services ranking average. Right image: Ecosystem services ranking average from frequency higher than 50%.

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The CoP members of Mediterranean case study have ranked the Ecosystem services from 1 to 4,5, being the first five ES ranked in Annex Table 21 as the most important to their MPAs, ranging from a rank of 1.1 to a rank of 1,92. These ES are the followings:

- Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy
- Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes
- Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection
- Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy
- Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value

Between these five ES better ranked, two have an average percentage of answers from the total possible higher than 50%. These ES are:

- Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes
- Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection

The CoP members of the Mediterranean case have given importance to regulation Ecosystem Services.

The results obtained regarding the relationship between ecosystem services and socio-economic criteria can be collectively reviewed for all case studies in section 3.3 (all sea basins) of the results.

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ATLANTIC SEA: THE AZORES CASE SITE

Annex Table 22: Summary of case site: Atlantic Sea. The Azores

ATLANTIC SEA (THE AZORES)	
	<p>Location: Atlantic Sea (The Azores)</p> <p>Name of MPA: It is a part of the limpets catch area, already described in a specific legislation</p> <p>Type of MPA: Sustainable use - IV in IUCN MPA type.</p> <p>MPA Plan: The area has not management plan</p>
<p>About the process of CoP interaction to execute 4.1</p>	<p>Several contacts via e-mails and phone calls were made to engage CoP members. In the Graciosa case study, as pointed out in the first interaction, some participants are not computer-lettered. These require some time, different resources or presential meetings.</p> <p>Some contacts were made to clarify some points with the Task Leaders. The second meeting of the Graciosa CoP took place on 15 June 2023 at 15:00 hrs (AZOR). Only two CoP members were present and participated actively in collaborative work. This was done in an interaction session on the Miro board.</p>

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	<p>The discussion was held based on the purple cracked limpets catching area in Picture XX below. Participants found the methodology complex, although they were able to develop it with guidance. It was explained to those present, that the methodology was also being tested with CoP members, and failures were also a result. Some questions arose when developing the work, for example: on the extraction area regarding harbour dredging or non-metallic mineral resources. It was suggested that the prioritisation of criteria could be done with values (1, 2 or 3 for example) to facilitate ranking. It was also suggested that the valuation of ecosystem services could also be valued from 0 to 100%. It was also pointed out that, as members of public management and with the perception of each one from their function, they can bring some specific questions to this model, which will continue to be developed.</p> <p>One extra effort was made to travel to Faial Island, where some CoP members live. Unfortunately, meeting with them was impossible because of agenda constraints. The time was a very busy period for most of them.</p> <p>After some insistence, it was possible to have one more feedback with an extra meeting. Some extra efforts are being made in order to perform the ranking properly.</p>
<p>Adjustments made to adapt the exercise to the test site</p>	<p>All the documents were translated into Portuguese in order to develop a better understanding.</p>
<p>Main challenges faced in completing the exercise</p>	<p>To engage stakeholders was the most difficult part. If it was not possible to complete Task 4.1, please explain the reason: Misunderstanding of the ranking.</p>
<p>Main ecosystems</p>	<p>Birds: Actitis macularius; Arenaria interpres; Bulweria bulwerii; Calidris alba; Calidris marítima; Calonectris borealis; Larus cachinnans; Larus fuscus; Larus hyperboreus; Larus marinus; Larus michahellis; Oceanodrama castro; Oceanodrama monteirol; Onychoprion ; fuscatus; Puffinus baroli; Puffinus puffinus; Sterna douglalli; Sterna hirundo Mammal: Physter macrocephalus Turtle: Chelonia mydas</p>

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Objectives of the MPA	The area is not a stablished MPA with objectives.
Main socio-economic characteristics of the MPA	It is an important area for limpet catch from artisanal fishermen

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Governance criteria analysis

Annex Figure 12: Average of governance criteria prioritization of The Azores. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 23: Average value of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - The Azores

Criterion	Priority	SD
CG_12	4,0	0,00
CG_1	3,7	0,58
CG_3	3,7	0,58
CG_4	3,7	0,58
CG_5	3,7	0,58
CG_13	3,7	0,58
CG_2	3,5	0,71
CG_6	3,3	0,58
CG_11	3,3	0,58
CG_7	3,0	0,00
CG_8	3,0	1,73
CG_9	2,5	2,12
CG_10	NAN	NAN

The Cop members of the Azores test site have scored most of the Governance criteria as “High Priority” criteria (Annex Figure 12, Annex Table 23). Attention should be given to the fact that only the highest scored criterion has a standard deviation below than 0,5. The higher punctuation was given to the next seven “high priority” criteria:

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CG_12. Strategic Environmental Assessment

CG_1. Ecosystem based management approach

CG_3. Coherence management of the area

CG_4. Stakeholder participation

CG_5. Equity

CG_13. Monitoring and evaluation

The criterion CG9 “Climate change measures established” was scored as the less important criterion for the Azores CoP members.

Criterion	Average Priority	Most Common Rank	Frequency *
CG_5	3,7	1	100%
CG_7	3,0	1	100%
CG_8	3,0	2	100%
CG_9	2,5	3	100%
CG_13	3,7	4	100%
CG_11	3,3	5	100%
CG_3	3,7	6	100%
CG_2	3,5	7	100%
CG_6	3,3	8	100%
CG_4	3,7	9	100%
CG_1	3,7	10	100%
CG_10	NAN	NAN	NAN
CG_12	4,0	NAN	NAN
* Only one person has answered this exercise.			

Annex Figure 13: Governance criteria ranking, average priority, and frequency of answers for rank - - The Azores

When asked about ranking the most important governance criteria, CoP member of Azores ranked the following five:

CG_5. Equity

CG_7. Clear strategic plan for the development of sustainable blue economy

CG_8. Sustainable fishing management

CG_9. Climate change measures established

CG_13. Monitoring and evaluation

The worst ranked criteria is the **CG_1** “Ecosystem based management approach”. Attention should be given to the fact that the ranking is not coincident with the prioritization of the criteria made in previous exercise. Indeed, the worst ranked criterion is at the same time the second criterion voted as “high priority”.

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Socio-economic criteria analysis

Annex Figure 14: Average of governance criteria prioritization of The Azores. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 24: Average value of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - The Azores

Criterion	Azores	SD
CSE_8	4,00	0,00
CSE_16	4,00	0,00
CSE_7	3,50	0,71
CSE_15	3,50	0,71
CSE_19	3,50	0,71
CSE_20	3,50	0,71
CSE_4	3,33	0,58
CSE_9	3,00	NAN
CSE_17	3,00	0,00
CSE_11	2,67	1,53
CSE_3	2,33	1,15
CSE_2	2,00	1,41
CSE_10	2,00	NAN
CSE_12	2,00	1,00
CSE_13	2,00	1,00
CSE_14	2,00	1,41
CSE_18	2,00	NAN
CSE_1	1,67	1,15

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CSE_5	1,00	NAN
CSE_6	1,00	NAN

The Cop members of the Azores have given the higher priority (with 0 deviation in the responses) to the criteria **CSE8** “The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality“ and **CSE16** “Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users“. The other most prioritized criteria (0,71 of deviation) are:

CSE7. Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.

CSE15. Area is important with occurrence of iconic species/habitats for the local community.

CSE19. Area is important for educational interest

CSE20. An area that has high scientific interest.

On the other hand, the socio-economic criterion 5 “Area is important for dredging” and 6 “Area is important for locally-caught seafood” were the lowest scored.

Annex Table 25: Socio-Economic criteria ranking. average priority, and frequency of answers for rank – The Azores Test Site

CG	Mean priority	Rank	Frequency*
CSE_16	4,0	1	100%
CSE_7	3,5	2	100%
CSE_3	2,3	3	100%
CSE_4	3,3	4	100%
CSE_2	2,0	5	100%
CSE_11	2,7	6	100%
CSE_12	2,0	7	100%
CSE_13	2,0	7	100%
CSE_17	3,0	8	100%
CSE_15	3,5	9	100%
CSE_8	4,0	10	100%
CSE_1	1,7	NAN	NAN
CSE_5	1,0	NAN	NAN
CSE_6	1,0	NAN	NAN
CSE_9	3,0	NAN	NAN
CSE_10	2,0	NAN	NAN
CSE_14	2,0	NAN	NAN
CSE_18	2,0	NAN	NAN
CSE_19	3,5	NAN	NAN
CSE_20	3,5	NAN	NAN

*Frequency is 100% because only one person has answered this exercise.

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In the Azores test site, the criteria 16, 7, 3, 4 and 2 were ranked in the first positions. These criteria are:

CSE_16. Area is important to be managed due to spatial conflicts among users.

CSE_7. Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.

CSE_3. Area is important for the development of blue economy activities

CSE_4. Area is important for shipping

CSE_2. Area is important for fishery activity

Ecosystem services analysis

Annex Table 26: Ecosystem services analysis: rank average and percentage of answers from the total possible – The Azores.

Ecosystem Services	Ranking average	Percentage of answers from the total possible*
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	1,33	100%
Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	1,5	100%
Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g. caves; Natural e.g. whales)	1,8	100%
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	2,0	100%
Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	2,0	100%
Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	2,0	100%
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	2,3	100%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	2,33	100%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	2,5	100%
* Only one person has done this exercise		

Annex Figure 15: The Azores - Ecosystem services ranking average

In this case, Annex Figure 15 does not include the graph related to the ranking of ecosystem services with a response frequency greater than 50% due to the absence of more than 1 respondent (every frequency is then 100%).

The CoP members of Azores case study have ranked the Ecosystem services from 1,33 to 2,5, being the first three ES ranked in Annex Table 26 and Annex Figure 14 as the most important to their MPAs, ranging from a rank of 1.33 to a rank of 1,8. These ES are the followings:

- Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)
- Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes
- Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g. caves; Natural e.g. whales).

The results obtained regarding the relationship between ecosystem services and socio-economic criteria can be collectively reviewed for all case studies in section 3.3 (all sea basins) of the results.

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BLACK SEA CASE SITE

Annex Table 27: Summary of case site. Black Sea

BLACK SEA																									
	<p>Location: Bulgarian part of Black Sea</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th style="text-align: center;">Name of Protected Area</th> <th style="text-align: center;">Legislation/Directive</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">1</td> <td>BG0000154 „Ezero Lake Durankulak”</td> <td>Natura 2000, Habitats Directive</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">2</td> <td>BG0000621 „Ezero Lake Shabla–Ezerets“</td> <td>Natura 2000, Habitats Directive</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">3</td> <td>BG0000573 „Kompleks Complex Kaliakra”</td> <td>Natura 2000, Habitats Directive</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">4</td> <td>BG0002050 „Durankulak Lake”</td> <td>Natura 2000, Birds Directive</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">5</td> <td>BG0000156 „Shablenski ezeren kompleks“</td> <td>Natura 2000, Birds Directive</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">6</td> <td>BG0002051 „Kaliakra “</td> <td>Natura 2000, Birds Directive</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">7</td> <td>“Kaliakra Reserve”</td> <td>National legislation</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>Type of MPA: The area includes a total number of 7 MPAs (under overlapping types of protection):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4. 3 Natura 2000 areas under the Birds Directive; 5. 3 Natura 2000 areas under the Habitats Directive; 6. 1 MPA under national legislation (National Reserve, IUCN 1a category). <p>What all 7 MPAs have in common is that they have both land and sea components.</p> <p>MPA Plan: No, there is no one management plan into force.</p>		Name of Protected Area	Legislation/Directive	1	BG0000154 „Ezero Lake Durankulak”	Natura 2000, Habitats Directive	2	BG0000621 „Ezero Lake Shabla–Ezerets“	Natura 2000, Habitats Directive	3	BG0000573 „Kompleks Complex Kaliakra”	Natura 2000, Habitats Directive	4	BG0002050 „Durankulak Lake”	Natura 2000, Birds Directive	5	BG0000156 „Shablenski ezeren kompleks“	Natura 2000, Birds Directive	6	BG0002051 „Kaliakra “	Natura 2000, Birds Directive	7	“Kaliakra Reserve”	National legislation
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6	BG0002051 „Kaliakra “	Natura 2000, Birds Directive																							
7	“Kaliakra Reserve”	National legislation																							
<p>About the process of CoP interaction to execute 4.1</p>	<p>The questions on the topic are specific, so all the CoP members from the Bulgarian side were contacted by phone to introduce in advance, and not all members were well</p>																								

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	<p>acquainted with the matter, which is why they refused to participate in the survey. The survey was conducted by two experts from the CCMS MSP4BIO team, as well as one member of the CoP, a representative of an environmental NGO. The questions were in English, and the materials (in excel and word) were sent by email. Respondents had one week to get introduced to the materials and to respond. For greater objectivity, each of the respondents works completely independently, without getting to know the answers and opinions of the others.</p>
Adjustments made to adapt the exercise to the test site	<p>It was decided to focus the exercise on already existing MPAs in the western part of the Black Sea (Bulgarian test site). The exercise was designed so that it could be completed individually without having a separate meeting.</p>
Main challenges faced in completing the exercise	<p>The topic is not well studied in the country. Some of the criteria are similar to others, which causes confusion. There is a comment from a CoP member that it took over 4 hours to complete. There were questions as to whether it was a current state or their perception (we clarified that it was their perception)</p>
Main ecosystems	<p>At sea, the Natura 2000 Habitats MPAs protect 2 species groups:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 2 Fishes (Alosa immaculate and Alosa tanaica); · 2 Marine mammals (Phocoena phocoen or Common Porpoise and Tursiops truncates or Bottle-nosed Dolphin). <p>The important habitats that are protected in the marine area are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 1110 Sandbanks which are slightly covered by sea water all the time; · 1150 Coastal lagoons; · 1160 Large shallow inlets and bays; · 1170 Reefs; · 1210 Annual vegetation of drift lines; · 1240 Vegetated sea cliffs of the Mediterranean coasts with endemic Limonium spp; · 8330 Submerged or partially submerged sea caves. <p>The test site is also an important bird's area as Via Pontica, the second largest bird migratory route in Europe, passes through here.</p>
Objectives of the MPA	<p>Still, no management plan has been put into force.</p>

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Main socio-economic characteristics of the MPA	The area is still naturally preserved and low urbanised. Main activities include: fishing, coastal/beach tourism, navigation/marine traffic, defence area for military training exercises, oil and gas extraction, also aquaculture is developed nearby to the area.
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Governance criteria analysis

Annex Figure 16: Average of governance criteria prioritization of Black Sea. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 28: Average value of governance criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - Black Sea.

Criterion	Black Sea	SD
CG_1	4,0	0,0
CG_2	4,0	0,0
CG_4	4,0	0,0
CG_10	4,0	0,0
CG_3	3,7	0,6
CG_8	3,7	0,6
CG_11	3,7	0,6
CG_12	3,7	0,6
CG_5	3,3	0,6
CG_6	3,3	0,6
CG_9	3,3	0,6
CG_7	3,0	0,0
CG_13	3,0	0,0

As can be seen in Annex Figure 16 and Annex Table 28, the CoP members of Black Sea case study (Bulgarian part) have ranked the Governance criteria from 3 to 4, which means that all the governance criteria are ranked as “priority” or “high priority” criteria in the MPAs evaluated. The higher ranked criteria to the Black Sea MPAs are:

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- CG1. Ecosystem based management approach
- CG2. Long term strategic adaptive management
- CG4. Stakeholder participation
- CG10. Cross-border cooperation

It is important to highlight that the aforementioned criteria have no standard deviation in the responses, although to this case site there is no deviation higher than 0.6.

Annex Table 29: Governance criteria ranking, average priority, and frequency of answers for rank - Black Sea.

Criterion	Average Priority	Most Common Rank	Frequency
CG_2	4,0	1	67%
CG_10	4,0	2	67%
CG_8	3,7	3	67%
CG_1	4,0	4	67%
CG_4	4,0	7	67%
CG_12	3,7	8	67%
CG_9	3,3	11	67%
CG_13	3,0	13	67%
CG_3	3,7	NAN	0%
CG_5	3,3	NAN	0%
CG_6	3,3	NAN	0%
CG_7	3,0	NAN	0%
CG_11	3,7	NAN	0%

NaN. No one with same answer, not result to show.

As can be seen in Annex Table 29, all the most ranked criteria were also scored with high priority. The best ranked governance criteria are:

CG2. Long term strategic adaptive management

CG10. Cross-border cooperation

CG8. Sustainable fishing management

CG1. Ecosystem based management approach

The worst ranked, with a 13 position, was **CG13** "Monitoring and evaluation".

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Socio-economic criteria analysis

Annex Figure 17: Average of socio-economic criteria prioritization of Black Sea. Values higher and equal to 3 indicate Priority and high priority. Standard Deviation (SD) is shown in red (right axes).

Annex Table 30: Average value of socio-economic criteria prioritization and respective standard deviation (SD) - Black Sea

Criterion	Average Priority	SD
CSE_1	3,67	0,58
CSE_2	3,67	0,58
CSE_7	3,67	0,58
CSE_8	3,67	0,58
CSE_9	3,67	0,58
CSE_11	3,67	0,58
CSE_13	3,67	0,58
CSE_3	3,33	0,58
CSE_14	3,33	0,58
CSE_17	3,33	0,58
CSE_18	3,33	0,58
CSE_20	3,33	0,58
CSE_4	3,00	0,00
CSE_10	3,00	0,00
CSE_12	2,67	0,58
CSE_15	2,67	0,58
CSE_19	2,67	0,58
CSE_6	2,33	0,58
CSE_16	2,33	0,58

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CSE_5	1,00	1,41
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The Cop members of the Black Sea have given priority to many of the proposed socio-economic criteria, although most of them were scored with a standard deviation higher than 0.5. Anyway, there are seven criteria with a higher prioritization score, they are:

CSE_1. Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities

CSE_2. Area is important for fishery activity

CSE_7. Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.

CSE_8. The area is important due to the socio-cultural dependence of the coastal community with its environmental quality.

CSE_9. Area is important for traditional human settlement, land-use, or sea-use which is representative of a culture, or human interaction with the environment.

CSE_11. Area important for recreation and leisure.

CSE_13. Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc).

On the other hand, the socio-economic criterion 5 “Area is important for dredging”, was scored with the lowest priority in this case study, due the lack of dredging activities in the test site.

Annex Table 31: Socio-Economic criteria ranking, average priority, and frequency of answers for rank - Black Sea Test Site.

C_Socio-economic	Mean Average	Most Common Rank	Frequency
CSE_7	3,67	1	66,7%
CSE_2	3,67	2	66,7%
CSE_13	3,67	3	66,7%
CSE_1	3,67	4	66,7%
CSE_11	3,67	7	66,7%
CSE_14	3,33	8	100,0%
CSE_3	3,33	9	66,7%
CSE_12	2,67	10	66,7%
CSE_15	2,67	11	66,7%
CSE_18	3,33	12	66,7%
CSE_20	3,33	13	66,7%
CSE_17	3,33	14	66,7%
CSE_10	3,00	15	66,7%
CSE_16	2,33	16	66,7%
CSE_4	3,00	nan	nan
CSE_5	1,00	nan	nan
CSE_6	2,33	nan	Nan

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CSE_8	3,67	nan	nan
CSE_9	3,67	nan	nan
CSE_19	2,67	nan	Nan

The CoP members of the Black Sea have ranked the following four socio-economic criteria as the most important to their case site:

CSE_7. Area has high scenic and/or aesthetic value.

CSE_2. Area is important for fishery activity.

CSE_13. Area is important because of the presence of structure with significant historical and cultural (monuments, etc).

CSE_1. Area is important for the generation of employment and income linked to no traditional activities.

On the other hand, criterion 16 “Area is important because allows the access to relevant areas for the marine users” was ranked in the last position in terms of its importance to the case study.

Attention should be given to the fact that every criterion was ranked with a percentage of occurrence higher than 66%.

Ecosystem services analysis

Annex Table 32: Ecosystem services analysis: rank average and percentage of answers from the total possible - Black Sea

Ecosystem Services	Ranking average	Percentage of answers from the total possible
Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes	1,1	83%
Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	1,6	89%
Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection	1,6	67%
Water conditions	2,0	33%
Atmospheric composition and conditions	2,0	33%
Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions	2,0	33%
Water used for nutrition, materials or energy	2,0	67%

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Physical and experiential interactions with the environment (abiotic e.g. caves; Natural e.g. whales)	2,7	85%
Wild plants (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy	2,7	61%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	2,8	90%
Mineral substances used for nutrition, materials or energy	3,1	83%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	3,3	94%
Intellectual and representative interactions with environment (abiotic and natural)	3,3	91%
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	3,3	78%
Reared aquatic animals for nutrition, materials or energy	3,4	67%
Other biotic characteristics that have a non-use value	3,8	90%
Regulation of baseline flows and extreme events	4,0	33%
Spiritual, symbolic and other interactions with natural environment	4,1	100%
Cultivated aquatic plants for nutrition, materials or energy	4,2	89%
Pest and disease control	4,3	44%
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	4,4	78%
Mediation of wastes or toxic substances of anthropogenic origin by living processes	5,0	100%
Other mineral or non-mineral substances or ecosystem properties used for nutrition, materials or energy	5,0	33%
Genetic material from all biota (division). Groups: Genetic material from plants, algae or fungi; Genetic material from animals; Genetic material from organisms.	5,0	56%
Mediation of nuisances of anthropogenic origin	6,0	33%

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Annex Figure 18: Black Sea - Left Image: Ecosystem services ranking average. Right image: Ecosystem services ranking average from frequency higher than 50%.

The CoP members of Black Sea case study have ranked the Ecosystem services from 1.1 to 6, being the first seven ES ranked in Annex Table 32, as the most important to their MPAs, ranging from a rank of 1.1 to a rank of 2. These ES are the following:

- Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes
- Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy
- Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection
- Water conditions
- Atmospheric composition and conditions
- Maintenance of physical, chemical, abiotic conditions
- Water used for nutrition, materials or energy

Between these seven ES better ranked, four have an average percentage of answers from the total possible higher than 50%. These ES are:

- Other type of regulation and maintenance service by abiotic/biotic processes
- Wild animals (terrestrial and aquatic) for nutrition, materials or energy
- Lifecycle maintenance, habitat and gene pool protection
- Water used for nutrition, materials or energy

The CoP members of the Black Sea have given importance to provisioning and regulation Ecosystem Services.

The results obtained regarding the relationship between ecosystem services and socio-economic criteria can be collectively reviewed for all case studies in section 3.3 (all sea basins) of the results.